

Project report

Embedded detection of atrial fibrillation and atrial flutter in single-channel ECG

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Dedicated to the millions of people around the world suffering from atrial fibrillation

Declaration of authorship

I hereby certify that this project report has been composed by me and is based on my own work, unless stated otherwise. No other person's work has been used without due acknowledgement in this thesis. All references and verbatim extracts have been quoted, and all sources of information, including graphs and data sets, have been specifically acknowledged¹.

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Saarbrücken, July 22, 2020

¹Source: https://www.phil-fak.uni-duesseldorf.de/uploads/media/Declaration_of_Authorship.pdf

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List of abbreviations

ADC	Analog Digital Converter, to read analogue signals for digital processing
AFE	Analog Front End, here an ADC with its analogue input circuits in one chip
BT	Bluetooth, a wireless communication standard
CPU	Central Processing Unit, computer processor
DAC	Digital Analog Converter, to output analogue signals
DSP	Digital Signal Processing
ECG	Electrocardiography, measuring electrical activity of the heart
EMI	Electro-Magnetic Interference
ESD	Electro-Static Discharge, a risk for electronic circuits
FIR	Finite Impulse Response, a type of digital filter in DSP
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform, transforms into the frequency domain
GPIO	General Purpose Input Output
HRV	Heart Rate Variability, natural variation of heartbeat durations
IIR	Infinite Impulse Response, another type of digital filter
I/O	Input / Output
LAN	Local Area Network
LED	Light Emitting Diode
NSR	Normal Sinus Rhythm, regular heart rhythm
OLED	Organic LED, a display technology
OS	Operating System
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
PC	Personal Computer
PCX	PiCture eXchange, a classic graphics file format
PNG	Portable Network Graphics, a graphics file format
QRS	Sequence of 3 central spikes, Q, R and S, in the human ECG
RAM	Random Access Memory, used as computer working memory
RMS	Root Mean Square
SoC	System on a Chip, containing CPU, RAM, I/O all on one chip
SPI	Serial Peripheral Interconnect, a serial interface standard
IPS TFT LCD	In-Plane Switching Thin-Film Transistor Liquid Crystal Display
UART	Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter, serial interface controller
USB	Universal Serial Bus, a serial interface family
WLAN	Wireless LAN, also called WiFi

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The idea for this projects originates from a meeting with Dr. med. Thomas Doerr, at his cardiology surgery in Zweibrücken. He is also active on the market for ECG (electrocardiography) products, including a device for recording ECG with a smartphone for telemetry purposes, so his professional activities combine medical, engineering and commercial aspects. A widespread health risk factor are atrial fibrillation (a-fib) and atrial flutter, in particular among older people.

As described in [Menche], page 239, pathological electrical activity loops can cause atrial activation at 250 to 350 beats per minute (atrial flutter) or even faster (atrial fibrillation, which is a lot faster than a physiological ventricular rhythm. Luckily, the ventricles often do not follow the pathological atrial rhythm. Instead, part of the atrial impulses fail to trigger ventricular activity and a regular or irregular ventricular rhythm still provides near-normal blood circulation. The decimation of high frequency atrial signals by the ventricles acts as a heart block. However, apart from palpitations when rhythms are irregular, and during episodes of high pulse rate (tachycardia), atrial fibrillation itself may go unnoticed by patients. The main problem with this is that less smooth blood flow during uncoordinated atrial activity causes an increased risk of blood clotting, without other symptoms as warning signs. Blood clots can then move to the lungs, causing pulmonary embolism, or block blood supply to other organs. This means that a-fib increases the risk for cerebral infarction. If ventricular activation does not sufficiently decimate atrial impulses, dangerously fast tachycardia can occur.

Given the high prevalence², associated risks and possibility of mild or unnoticed symptoms, it is desirable to have an easy way of knowing whether a person is experiencing atrial fibrillation at a given moment. To avoid having to see a doctor for recording a high quality ECG, an affordable device for home use can be a solution for quick evaluation. The device could record the ECG and a trained person could review the recording after the patient uses a telemetry infrastructure to upload the recording. However, this again raises the bar for quickly evaluating whether or not the patient experiences a-fib. Also, telemetry may violate user privacy. A good solution can be a device which integrates recording and processing to directly provide an a-fib likelihood rating to the patient, who can then decide whether and when to share ECG data or see a doctor for further investigation.

Some patients may also have countermeasures available, such as medication against irregular heart rhythms or against blood clotting, so they could adjust their dosage within limits agreed upon with their cardiologist, based on the ECG evaluation provided by the device. It is important to notice that a simple device can never be the sole basis of therapeutical decisions, but it is good for the patient to have an easy way to evaluate their situation, similar to the widespread use of affordable home blood pressure meters.

According to Dr. Doerr, smartwatches, fitness trackers and similar consumer devices that provide insights about heart rhythms tend to focus on very coarse metrics such as the heart rate, measured by ECG, optical or possibly mechanical methods. The pathological mechanism of a-fib and atrial flutter can indeed cause machine-recognisable effects on heart rate variations.

One way to visualise those is a Poincaré Plot, which is a scatterplot using the durations of current and next R/R period (the time between heart contractions, in the ECG case between R-waves of the QRS complexes, which correspond to ventricular activation, see [Menche] page 236f). Looking at data from online ECG corpora, which will be discussed later in this report, a-fib can lead to very dispersed (chaotic changes of R/R from beat to beat), very compact (ventricular activity passes on atrial stimuli at a fixed rate) or clustered (variable subdivision of fixed atrial frequencies) while normal sinus rhythm exhibits more similarity between adjacent R/R periods, combined with

²Millions of cases, <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11343485/>

healthy slow variations of the heart rate over time, based on breathing, physical activity, autonomous nervous system and other factors.

1.2 Evaluating ECG Morphology

While this makes it possible to extract evidence for whether or not a person is experiencing a-fib by evaluating their R/R data over a short period, Dr. Doerr criticises this method as too indirect. Instead, he recommends to record a sufficiently clear ECG and evaluate the relationship between P-waves, corresponding to the atrial activity ([Menche] page 236) and the QRS complexes. Having high amplitude, the latter are easy to detect even in noisy recordings, while the former have low amplitudes, which make them harder to measure with simple equipment. As a work-around, the ECG can be averaged over several heart cycles:

Figure 1.1: Schema of normal ECG with main wave and segment labels, source: Hank van Helvete on Wikimedia.org, CC-BY-SA license

As known from signal processing theory, the signal to noise ratio of (quasi-) periodic signals can be improved by a factor of N by averaging N squared periods of the signal, because the noise will not be phase-locked to the signal and will be reduced by averaging. This is used for example in ABR (auditory brainstem response) and OAE (otoacoustic emissions) measurements.

While Dr. Doerr suggested pooling into two or three alternating groups, based on experience with bigeminy or trigeminy rhythms, my algorithm used in this project instead measures the RMS (root mean square) values of the individual beats and of all pairwise beat differences to select a subset of matching beats to average.

Once averaged, even the ECG recorded with simple hardware and simple electrodes should have sufficient quality to generate metrics about P-waves and their relation to QRS complexes.

Figure 1.1 shows a schematic overview of a normal sinus rhythm ECG: The P-wave corresponds to atrial activity, while the high amplitude QRS complex corresponds to ventricular activation

and the T-wave is linked to ventricular relaxation. The durations of the various waves, the delay between them and the amplitudes of the waves and the intervals between them are all suitable as metrics for evaluating various aspects of the physiological and pathological activity of the heart using ECG recordings. As mentioned, this project will focus on the P-wave (<https://litfl.com/p-wave-ecg-library/>) and its relative timing ahead of the QRS complex, the PR-interval (<https://litfl.com/pr-interval-ecg-library/>). Note that the relative amplitudes and morphologies of the Q, R and S part can vary a lot (<https://litfl.com/qrs-interval-ecg-library/>) so some flexibility in QRS detection will be necessary.

This project focuses on analysis of Einthoven lead I recordings, as those are easiest for the patient to take: The patient simply has to connect the device to both wrists or hands. While lead II provides better amplitudes, it involves a hand and a leg. Multi channel recordings also involve precordial (chest) leads, which is out of our scope for easy use by the patient. Proper chest lead locations ([Menche] page 236) also are not intuitive to casual users.

1.3 Choice of Hardware

Dr. Doerr suggested using the HeartyPatch embedded ECG platform for the project. However, as explained in section 2.1, it turned out to be not available in Europe. As the hardware seemed to be very appropriate for the project, the alternative solution was to acquire another embedded platform with the same chipset: The ESP32 system on a chip and the MAX30003 ECG analogue front-end. Details about those are provided in section 2.1. Different from what the HeartyPatch platform would have offered, this project also uses a number of colour LED (light emitting diode) and a small OLED (organic LED) colour display, which allows more versatile output options. The used ESP32 board is based on the ESP32-WROOM-32 module, which integrates the ESP32 chip with a suitable antenna for wireless communications into a small surface mountable circuit board.

1.4 Future Hardware

As part of a M.Sc. thesis, a low cost device integrating a custom MAX30003 board with the ESP32-WROOM-32 module and a display module could be developed. For example a 96×64 or 128×64 pixel OLED (Organic LED) or a 160×80 or 240×240 pixel colour IPS TFT LCD (liquid crystal display) with SPI (Serial Peripheral Interconnect) connectivity can be used here. Such displays are available for around 10 € from brands like Waveshare even from smaller shops.

Inspired by other products, Dr. Doerr suggested a stick shaped device which the user can grab to record an Einthoven lead I ECG and get a traffic light style classification using LED built into the product. Based on my experience with this project, I suggest a design with several LED and a screen to be able to report more verbose analysis results to the user while still keeping the main outcome of the analysis easy to understand, for example using one or more bargraphs or colour LED to indicate the likelihood of a-fib or flutter. Due to unforeseen epidemic circumstances, no further meetings have taken place in this project, but it would be interesting to consider cooperation with Dr. Doerr and his patients for future projects.

As the MAX30003 features low power lead detection, it should be possible to let the ESP32 hibernate until the user touches the leads. That way, there is no need for a power switch or buttons to trigger measurements, making use of the device even easier. The support for wireless communications protocols can be used to enable Bluetooth telemetry of analysis results to a PC, phone or tablet at the option of the user, provided there are suitable precautions in place against data leakage to eavesdroppers. Those could be as simple as a connect button or the display of a random code on the device which has to be known by those who want to establish a wireless connection.

2 System Design

2.1 Hardware and Toolchain

The HeartyPatch (<https://www.crowdsupply.com/protocentral/heartypatch>) would have been a suitable platform for the project. It is a <https://heartypatch.protocentral.com/> crowd-funded design and uses the MAX30003 chip by Maxim Integrated (<https://datasheets.maximintegrated.com/en/ds/MAX30003.pdf>) as integrated ECG analogue front-end (AFE). This chip can record single-channel ECG at up to 512 samples per second at 16 bit resolution and features built-in R/R detection. ESD (electro-static discharge) protection, DC filter, amplifier, ADC (analogue digital converter) and digital interface are all built into the chip as well. HeartyPatch connects it to the ESP32 system on a chip (<https://www.espressif.com/en/products/socs/esp32/overview>) which contains a fast dual core embedded CPU (central processing unit), more than 500 kilobytes of working memory and a variety of interfaces, importantly including SPI (serial peripheral interconnect), Bluetooth, wireless network (WLAN / WiFi) and serial ports.

One of the latter is connected to an USB (Universal Serial Bus) to serial port bridge chip for data exchange and in-circuit programming. The HeartyPatch is open hardware, circuit diagrams and PCB (printed circuit board) layout are freely available on the homepage, as well as open source: A demo firmware with R/R based HRV (heart rate variability) processing and wireless streaming connectivity is available as open source.

The necessary ESP32 toolchain is freely available from espressif and most easily used via the Arduino IDE (<https://www.arduino.cc/> Integrated Development Environment) after adding the ESP32 repository as described in the appendix. A free stand alone compiler is available as well, but using Arduino has the advantage of being able to use a stable set of run-time libraries including easy access to all peripherals including the wireless communication on a pre-configured FreeRTOS installation (<https://www.freertos.org/>) as embedded real-time operating system.

However, it turned out that the HeartyPatch has no CE certification, which makes it impossible to import it into the EU. While it would have been a possibility to use the published data to build a clone of the original here, this would have been tedious and expensive.

Instead, I have decided to combine easily available products with the same chipset: Maxim produces a demo board called MAX30003WING (<https://datasheets.maximintegrated.com/en/ds/MAX30003WING.pdf>) at a price around 30 € (the chip itself is 5 USD for large orders, around 9 € for one) which stacks on the Adafruit HUZZAH32 ESP32 Feather board (24 €). Available sampling rates of the MAX30003 (125 to 512 sps) are more than sufficient for morphological ECG analysis ([Pizzuti]). Selecting a multiple of 50 Hz, here 500 sps, made algorithmic simplifications possible.

The HUZZAH32 Feather (<https://learn.adafruit.com/adafruit-huzzah32-esp32-feather/>) board combines an ESP32-WROOM-32 module (circa 5 €), with the ESP32 chip and a matching wireless antenna in one convenient small package, with USB connectivity, a voltage regulator and a battery controller in a lab-friendly form factor.

While the HeartyPatch provides a single colour LED (light emitting diode) as indicator, the HUZZAH32 only has a simple red LED. I have selected a bar with 15 NeoPixel colour LED from Seed Studio (6 €) and a small OLED (organic LED) colour display (Waveshare, 96 × 64 pixels, 10 €) from my lab as output devices, which makes more detailed output of status, ECG and results possible.

The only input device is a set of 3 wrist (or ankle) band electrodes for EMG (electromyography, measures muscle signals) and ECG purposes from Olimex (16 €). Adhesive electrodes would improve signal quality (low, stable impedance) but are less suitable for spontaneous measurements and are not reusable. Figure 2.2 shows the complete setup with HUZZAH32, MAX30003WING, OLED and NeoPixels on a breadboard. The small extra voltage regulator board in the background is not used here: It could provide additional power for peripherals.

Figure 2.1: Embedded ecghelper device showing the ECG analysis screen

Power is provided either by USB from a PC or using a USB powerbank: The latter ensures that there are no ground loops and less 50 Hz mains power AC artefacts. It also improves user safety to have no, even indirect, connection to AC power. Details about the connections between the individual system components can be found in the appendix A.

Following the open source spirit behind the HeartyPatch, the software created for this project will be made available under the 2-clause BSD License, also known as Simplified BSD (Berkeley Software Distribution) License or FreeBSD License. That way, it will be possible for interested users of the HeartyPatch and similar hardware to run my algorithm on their devices and develop improved firmware for them.

2.2 Real-Time Signal Processing Chain

The standard structure of Arduino based applications starts at two functions provided by the user: setup, which is invoked once at boot, and loop, which is repeatedly called by the FreeRTOS real-time operating system in an infinite loop. While setup simply initialises data structures and drivers, the loop function in this project checks status flags of the MAX30003 whether at least 10 (threshold configurable) samples are available in the 32 sample capacity FIFO (first in, first out memory buffer). If yes, but there is an ongoing leads-off, fast recovery (out of range) or overflow status, samples are read and discarded and the recording restarts. The chip handles out of range conditions caused by DC drift by automatically modulating high-pass filtering when amplitudes exceed a configurable limit for some time.

The recording also restarts when a leads-on event is detected. It would be possible to program ESP32 and MAX30003 to raise an interrupt on such events and let the ESP32 hibernate until then, using very little energy until the user connects the electrodes. The current version conserves energy only by completely disabling wireless communications, which are not used yet for the project. Also, screen and LED are dimmed during leads-off state.

While samples are available during normal recording, they are read and sent to the `useSample()` function for filtering and storage. The newest filtered sample arriving in the recording buffer is also sent to `rrDetector()`, which returns true when the most recent sample has been classified as centre of a QRS complex (see figure 1.1) by the R/R detector. Detected QRS centres get recorded to a small list with currently 26 entries. When either the 30 second recording buffer is full or the QRS list is full, recording is stopped and the application moves on to the analysis step. Otherwise, the OLED screen is updated every 10 samples to show a scope view of the ongoing recording: 10 samples are one period of possible 50 Hz artefacts, which reduces the influence of AC hum on the

Figure 2.2: Embedded ecg helper device breadboard setup with stacked PCB, small OLED display and NeoPixel colour LED array

scope view. The central loop also checks QRS detections by the MAX30003 hardware itself and displays them by LED, as well as displaying other status flags by LED, as summarised in table 2.1.

Note that depending on the operation phase (recording versus analysis result display), meanings of LED indicators change. Details can be found in section 2.4. See section 2.3 for details about the analysis algorithm itself.

The main signal processing pipeline in real-time recording happens in `useSample()`, which first optionally passes the sample through a baseline correction filter: A long moving average tracks the baseline amplitude drift and returns the amplitude of incoming samples relative to the current baseline with half the window size delay. As this introduces a large latency and the MAX30003 already offers both analogue and digital (first order Butterworth IIR) baseline filters in hardware, only the analogue high-pass filter is used and the software baseline filter is disabled. Tests with pre-recorded ECG corpus data showed that the filter is not needed there either, as the analysis easily handles the amounts of baseline wander present in the corpus.

Next, the samples are passed through an optimised FIR (finite impulse response) filter and the filter output values are stored in a recording buffer. The filter combines a moving average of window size 10 with a high-pass filter to reduce the amplitude distortion for frequency components in the ECG which are relevant for the analysis: The moving average removes all periodic signal components with

LED Index	Colour	Meaning
0	red	recording error / Result: a-fib or atrial flutter
0	purple	Result: signal too noisy to classify
0	green	ongoing recording / Result: normal sinus rhythm
0	cyan	filter warm-up for recording start
0	cyan flash	detected QRS complex
1, 2	red	Result: a-fib or atrial flutter
1, 2, 3	purple	Result: signal too noisy to classify
1, 2, 3	green	Result: normal ECG / recording done
1	gradient	recording progress (black to red, yellow and white)
2	gradient	QRS detector warm-up (red to green)
2	flash	QRS complex detected / refractory period
3	red	Result: deviant or suspicious ECG
3	flash	MAX30003 hardware QRS detection
4	red	Result: periodogram score suggests a-fib or flutter (gradient)
4	green	Result: periodogram score suggests normal ECG (gradient)
5	red	Result: P-wave height suggests a-fib or flutter (gradient)
5	green	Result: P-wave height suggests normal ECG (gradient)
6	red	Result: minority of beats similar to each other (gradient)
6	green	Result: majority of beats similar to each other (gradient)

Table 2.1: Overview of NeoPixel LED usage in the ecghelper application, LED 0 being the main status LED which is controlled via the `errorBox()` function which also controls colour status bars on the OLED display.

10 samples (20 ms) or an integer fraction of that as period length. In other words, it removes 50 Hz AC mains hum artefacts and harmonics of that. The optimised filter reduces amplitude changes for signal components below 40 Hz to a range between 3 dB loss and 1.4 dB gain. Details can be found in section 2.2.2.

2.2.1 QRS Detection Component

In addition, all samples for the recording buffer are being passed through a QRS detector: The `rrDetector()` processing relies on a metric generated by `qrsFilter()` which is a Gaussian smooth second derivative filter truncated to 63 taps with small integer weights. It is most sensitive to frequencies between 6 and 15 Hz and reacts to changes in the derivative of the ECG, in other words to sharp turns in the ECG curve. While this filter uses 5 times more CPU than the FIR filter against AC artefacts (estimate based on profiling the Linux application) the entire real-time signal processing while recording ECG on the embedded system causes only around 10 percent CPU load on the ESP32 according to measurements of idle and busy time on the embedded system. Weights and frequency response are shown in figure 2.3. A good online and offline resource about digital signal processing is [Smith].

The filter approach has been chosen because the popular Pan and Tompkins algorithm ([Pan], see also the corresponding Wikipedia article for an overview) has a strong focus on keeping CPU load low. It has been developed around 1985 to detect QRS complexes in real-time applications on the simple Z80 CPU of that time, for 200 sps (samples per second) ECG recordings.

The ESP32 has a far more powerful CPU and the project uses 500 sps ECG recordings. Interestingly, the MAX30003 hardware R/R detection uses a modified Pan / Tompkins algorithm, too, which only has 8 ms time resolution because it internally works at lower sampling rates. This allows the chip to detect heartbeats in hardware while still only using 85 μ W of power in full operation.

Figure 2.3: Frequency response and weights of the integrated QRS detection filter, not showing the additional nonlinear squaring step or the sign-dependent scaling to implement partial rectification, to prefer positive over negative peaks

The Pan / Tompkin approach uses a 5 to 11 Hz IIR (infinite impulse response, with feedback) and FIR band-pass filter created from separate high-pass and low-pass stages with at most 5 taps each and only ± 1 , 2 and 32 as weights and simple bit-shifts to roughly normalise output gain. It then applies a 5 sample derivative kernel $(-2 \ -1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 2)$, which has good linearity below 30 Hz at 200 sps and squares the result, with saturation (limit results to 255). A moving window integrator with window size similar to QRS complex length generates a feature value which rises during the QRS complex, then stays constant for the window size before falling again. When the feature passes a dynamically determined threshold, the ECG signal itself is searched for a recent R peak.

There are elaborate heuristics to determine which feature events are actual signs of QRS detections: Peaks too short after other detections are rejected (refractory period) and the absence of peaks within a certain window around the expected R/R period unlocks the use of peaks above an alternate (half height) threshold, assuming missed peaks. By already tracking alternate peaks as they come in, no extra trace back search is needed. If two adjacent peaks are close to each other, the second peak is ignored if it has at most half the slope value of the first, to prevent peaked T-waves from being detected as QRS complexes.

The heuristics used for this project are less complex in the real-time recording phase: The smooth second derivative filter replaces band-pass, derivative and moving average by one single step, making use of the available powerful CPU.

Instead of just squaring the generated feature, positive second derivative FIR filter results are attenuated by a factor of four in `qrsFilter()` before squaring and returning the metric. This makes the filter prefer maxima (R-waves) over minima (S-waves), while still allowing negative peaks to be detected as a fallback when R peaks are too weak.

Producing a smooth peak with a defined latency for QRS complexes in the ECG, the described filter-generated feature is well suited for QRS detection, as shown for example in figure 2.4. The plot delays the filtered ECG to match the QRS feature timing, so both are plotted at the combined latency of both the QRS feature filter and the AC hum comb notch filter relative to the unfiltered raw signal (blue raw, red filtered, green and yellow QRS feature and feature edge).

Figure 2.4: Test signals: Scope view and analysis of an 80 bpm normal sinus rhythm with 50 Hz artefact, generated by the Fluke PS420 simulator. The input FIR filter blocks the artefact with minimal signal distortion and low latency. Filtered ECG (red) and QRS detector feature (green, yellow) align well after latency adjustment. In the analysis plot on the right, spikes mark key points in the ECG shape and the green curve (scale changes near QRS for readability!) indicates slope

Similar to Pan / Tompkins, my algorithm first tracks the highest feature value seen in the first 1.5 seconds of the recording to determine an initial detection threshold. It then triggers for each situation where the feature value stops rising while being above a dynamic threshold, also excluding a refractory period after each trigger. However, the dynamic threshold tracking is somewhat simplified compared to the Pan / Tompkins algorithm.

When the recording is complete or suitable amount of pre-recorded ECG has been read from a file, an offline heuristics step removes false positives such as T-waves triggering the QRS detector. This is sufficient for this project, as early false positives only bias the recording progress meter. As long as the final analysis phase finds enough clean beat segments, there will be no problem.

The Linux application for processing ECG corpus data does not track real-time progress. Instead, it uses at most 30 seconds of the available data, skipping early low-quality segments based on heuristics which check dynamic range and QRS detection moments.

A good overview of the landscape of possible QRS detection algorithms can be found in [Köhler]: While QRS complexes are clearly visible waveforms in the ECG, there are many approaches to detect them reliably. Their main frequencies are 10 to 25 Hz, so a filter can block lower frequency waveforms to focus on QRS. The high-pass property of differentiators is used in various algorithms.

Other algorithms combine features generated using several filter bands. The QRS complex itself can be found by finding maxima in features, usually with a dynamically updated threshold. Yet other approaches use Wavelet transforms, neural networks or Hidden Markov Models, which may require large sets of training data. A matched FIR filter can detect waveforms which are the time-reverse of their impulse response. Genetic algorithms have been applied to detect QRS complexes, as well as Hilbert transforms implemented with the help of FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) and FIR filters to track the signal envelope, sometimes combined with a moving average filter for smoothing.

On the other hand, methods with very low computational cost can work fine: Adding a high-frequency sequence of suitable amplitude to the band-pass filtered signal, the frequency of zero crossings goes down for segments with large amplitude such as the QRS complex, which allows detection by finding timespans of low zero crossing density based on a running average. As the article concludes, many high performance algorithms exist and there are algorithms with very

different computational loads. 4 of the 7 reviewed algorithms with the lowest computational load still show sensitivities and specificities both above 99 percent.

A selection of algorithms is available in the open source Biosigkit for Octave and Matlab [Sedghamiz], which also provides links to papers about each algorithm: Pan / Tompkins as described above, non-linear phase space reconstruction, a simple state machine to tag R-, S- and T-waves in real-time context, Wavelet-inspired filter bank feature combinations, multilevel Teager Energy Operator detection and a generic multiscale peak detection algorithm.

2.2.2 FIR Filter Design

To block 50 Hz AC harmonics as the main source of ECG recording artefacts, a filter which attenuates specifically that frequency and multiples of it is necessary. A very CPU efficient filter is a moving average FIR filter, which can be implemented by updating intermediate states adding one new sample at a time and removing one old sample at a time. Signal components which have an integer number of periods fit into the moving average window size will be cancelled out by the averaging. As 50 Hz signals have exactly 10 samples per period at the used sampling rate of 500 samples per second, a suitable filter is easy to implement. FIR filters have the advantage to have no feedback loops and they can be designed to have linear phase frequency response ([Smith]).

However, simple moving average filters also attenuate signal components at frequencies far away from the desired notch frequencies. In fact, they can make good low-pass filters. To improve signal preservation up to at least 40 Hz, a high-pass filter can be used to boost some of the frequencies attenuated by the moving average filter. Chaining two FIR filters is the same as convolving both filter weight vectors to create a set of weights for a single FIR filter, so the strategy was to search for a short FIR high-pass filter which, when combined with the moving average filter, minimises pass-band ripple up to 40 Hz, keeps the 50 Hz (and harmonics of that) notch characteristics strong and limits damping at the desired 40 Hz cut-off frequency to around 3 dB.

Finding a filter with suitable characteristics can be done by automatically generating and comparing a list of candidates. A 12 point FIR filter with circa 41 Hz (0.1635 times the Nyquist frequency here) corner frequency produces good results at low computational cost. Truncating the weight vector to 18 samples reduces cost even further without much distortion. It reduces notch depth from -93 dB to -44 dB at exactly 50 Hz, but only from 21.7 dB to 21.5 dB for a window of 0.5 Hz above and below 50 Hz.

```
pkg load signal;
firweights = conv(fir1(12, 0.1635, "high"), ones(1, 10) / 10);
firweights = firweights(3:end-2); % truncate from 22- to 18-tap
firweights = round(32768.0 * firweights / sum(firweights)) / 32768.0;
```

Note that the resulting filter has positive ripple up to 1.4 dB slightly above 20 Hz. This means some higher frequency ECG components such as the QRS complex will be amplified (emphasised) as side-effect of the filter.

Comprehensive simulations with sample ECG data and artificially added 50 Hz hum and noise show that the specialised FIR filter shows good results compared to a simple moving average, comparable to far more computationally expensive approaches such as high order filters or FFT. Another reason to use short filters is the desire to have low latencies in real-time processing and short transient oscillations when starting new measurements.

Figure 2.5: Left: Design and performance of a 10 sample moving average filter, with strong low-pass effect as well as a comb notch for AC harmonics rejection. Right: Optimised filter, convolving a moving average comb notch (reject AC harmonics) with a high-pass for better frequency response. The top plots show the filter weights and zoomed in sections of the frequency responses to highlight ripple. Note the different frequency scales.

Figure 2.6: Filtering a corpus excerpt with added 50 Hz hum and noise using a simple 20 ms moving average, FFT or advanced filters: QRS wear caused by low-pass properties of the moving average

Figure 2.7: Filtering a corpus excerpt with added 50 Hz hum and noise using an optimised short FIR filter, FFT or advanced filters: QRS wear reduced

2.3 Offline Analysis Phase

After gathering ECG data and spotting QRS complexes, recording stops (or the input file is closed, in the offline application) and the ecganalysis stage takes over: Data segments aligned around the QRS complexes are compared, to heuristically select a large subset of ECG beats which are similar to each other and represent the data well. This removes beats with strong artefacts, premature beats and similar.

An average of the selected segments is computed, which reduces the impact of signals which are not phase-locked to the QRS complexes, improving the signal to noise ratio. The averager takes exponential decay from the analogue high-pass filter of the MAX30003 into account by adding a configurable fraction of the area of the previous signal to each sample, after removing DC components, effectively undoing most of the filter effect for better low frequency fidelity. This is safe to do because the average is relatively free of unwanted low frequency components such as baseline drift.

Figure 2.8: Weights for the two available smooth slope filters: The current default is to use the longer filter, while the shorter filter can be selected as compile time option for less smoothing

The average is tuned further by attempting to flatten the part before QRS by selective regression analysis (excluding steep parts) which can help at high pulse rates where P-waves touch the trailing edge of the previous T-waves. The baseline of the average is re-evaluated, again considering slope and a suitable short binomial smooth derivative FIR filter, weights shown in figure 2.8, is used to help mapping the landscape of the ECG pulse shape. See also [Duan] for a discussion of possible baseline amplitude level measurement methods.

2.3.1 Periodogram Scoring

In a separate step, a periodogram of the entire ECG recording is generated, based on a simple central difference derivative of the data for clean recordings. If the periodogram shows signs of strong AC hum at the predetermined frequencies of 50, 60 or 187.25 Hz found in corpus data, derivative computation switches to smoother derivatives based on moving averages of appropriate sizes (10, 8 and empirically determined 5 samples respectively).

While the periodogram step caches the derivatives on the ESP32, having enough free working memory there, this step still causes the majority of the one second delay between recording and result presentation in the embedded `ecghelper` system. It is possible that FFT or similar algorithms can improve performance here. Using a periodogram has the advantage that the calculations are straightforward and easily done in fixed point arithmetics: The entire `ecghelper` application only uses fixed point, at most 32-bit, arithmetics to make it suitable for porting to various embedded platforms. The ESP32 itself also has hardware support for simple floating point operations, in particular for addition and multiplication of 32-bit floating point numbers.

The periodogram is smoothed and scanned for peaks. Based on their frequencies, they contribute with different weights to a score for atrial fibrillation and flutter risks. High scores always lead to classification of the recording as a-fib, medium scores are counted as risk factor. This is combined with the ECG morphology analysis, where clear violations always trigger a-fib classification, while risk factors trigger such classification only when combined with other risk factors such as suspicious periodogram scores.

2.3.2 ECG Morphology Analysis

The heart of the ECG classifier is the morphological analysis of the averaged ECG pulse shape. The core `analyzePulseShape()` function relies on the `findHalfPeak()` function for much of that work. The analysis starts by determining the R and S peak times by finding local minima or maxima, respectively. From there, the Q peak is located. Starting at Q and S, the half-peak search determines the time where the shape meets the baseline or otherwise gets flat (ST-segments are not necessarily at baseline). Having mapped the timespan of the QRS complex, windows before and after it are checked for boundary effects first: At high pulse rates, a large trailing part of the previous T-wave may still be visible near the P-wave, for example. Such zones are excluded from further search. Local maxima in the remaining time window before and after the QRS complex are treated as P- and T-wave peaks respectively, again using the half-peak helper to find onset and offset points.

Next, time windows before the QRS complex which are not yet linked to other classifications again are scanned for additional P-wave candidates. If such candidates do exist and their height is significant compared to the original P-wave, the ECG is immediately classified as atrial flutter or fibrillation. Flutter waves in relatively fixed phase relationships to the QRS complex are what the algorithm assumes to be the origin of such additional pseudo P-waves.

An example of the detected wave timings for an artificial normal sinus rhythm ECG signal from a patient simulator is shown in figure 2.4, which also illustrates the effectiveness of FIR filtering and averaging to get a very low-noise estimate of the underlying ECG pulse shape using affordable recording hardware in a very compact embedded device.

If no extra P-waves are present, the geometry of the main P-wave is used as main decision base for the algorithm: The P-wave has to be tall enough, compared to the QRS complex, in the averaged shape. As P-waves are relatively short, phase instabilities relative to the QRS timing will quickly shrink their amplitude in the averaged shape, which is used as a measure of a-fib risk by the algorithm. Likewise, irregular timings will distort the P-waves into a wide probability distribution hill, as opposed to a clear, relatively narrow peak. The algorithm uses this to reject both too flat and too long P-wave candidates. Also, the flatter shapes fail to have clear onset and offset moments, so runaway onsets long before the QRS complex also trigger ECG classification as a-fib. See also [Caldwell] for some reasoning about long P-waves in context of atrial pathologies.

2.3.3 Normal ECG Geometry Parameters

The expected ranges for various aspects of the ECG morphology are based on both data driven experiments with ECG corpora and values taken from generic or ECG specific websites, so this section lists a few of those. All values relate are based on website contents reviewed between March and May 2020 and were still listed on the sites in July.

<http://ems12lead.com/2014/03/10/understanding-ecg-filtering/>

Important spectral components of the P-wave are 2/3 to 5 Hz, for the T-wave 1 to 7 Hz and for the QRS complex 10 to 50 Hz, while muscle artefacts are mainly 5 to 50 Hz. A common artefact is AC mains hum (50 or 60 Hz). Pulse rates vary from 40 to 300 beats per minute, although the extremes are rarely physiological. ECG amplitudes have relevant features mainly between 0.1 and 2 mV, which is far below the 200 to 300 mV of DC which can build up at the electrode interfaces and even below voltage variations caused by lead movements. While low-pass filters distort mainly the QRS complex, high-pass filters (to remove baseline wander and breathing artefacts, breathing is 8 to 30 breaths per minute) can introduce phase distortions up to 5 to 10 times the cut-off frequency, in particular with analogue filters.

In this context it is relevant that the MAX30003 wing board uses the analogue high-pass filter at nominally 0.44 Hz (recommended for ambulatory use), not the patient monitoring 0.04 Hz option, while 0.05 to 150 Hz would be best for high fidelity recordings. Lower upper frequency limits of 40 or 100 Hz reduce muscle artefacts, but cause distortions in ST-segment and fine details such as epsilon- or J-waves, which are explained on the Life in the Fast Lane website:

<https://litfl.com/qrs-interval-ecg-library/>

Life in the Fast Lane, together with the articles about Osborn- or J-waves, mentions that ECG peak-peak amplitudes can reach 6 mV in pathological cases and 4.5 mV in physiological precordial lead ECG, which helped to select suitable gain settings for the MAX30003.

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electrocardiography>

The Wikipedia article about ‘ECG’ (also the German article) gives 80 ms as normal P-wave duration (pathological: inverted, longer than 100 ms, two-humped, peaked, taller than 250 μ V or in several different shapes) and 100 to 300 μ V as normal amplitude. The article titled ‘Atrial fibrillation’ not only estimates that there are 33 million cases around the world (and 200 000 deaths) but also mentions local rotors with 5.8 to 10 Hz oscillation frequency as source and presents a number of ECG plot examples. It also describes the P-wave shapes as irregular, sawtooth or artefact in a-fib and flutter, with a fixed or variable A/V conduction ratio leading to palpitations and fast pulse: If the age-specific filter to circa 220 minus age in years beats per minutes fails, dangerously fast pulse rates can occur. P-waves have corresponding repolarization waves of opposite polarity around 320 ms later, which are usually only visible in the form of distortions to the ST-segment or T-wave.

Other articles list the normal PR or PQ duration as 120 to 200 ms (longer in A/V heart block, long PR and QT in magnesium deficiency) and, in the article titled ‘QRS complex’, 80 to 120 ms as the normal QRS duration. However, children can have shorter complexes (60 ms, also seen in adults during physical activity) and bundle branch blocks can prolong QRS complexes to 120 ms and more. Looking at amplitudes, Q is usually less than one third of the R to S difference or a quarter of the R amplitude and at most 40 ms ahead of R. The article ‘Ventricular Activation Time’ is more specific and lists up to 30 or 50 ms depending on lead, which is important for the control of search scopes in the morphology analysis in this project. The articles about ‘T wave’ (duration circa 160 ms), ‘ST segment’ (normally flat, less than 100 μ V from baseline) and ‘QT interval’ provide additional important details.

In particular, the ‘QT interval’ article provides a list of established QTc formulae: The QT interval (from Q onset to T offset) is expected to stay within heart-rate dependent limits, which is tested

by computing corrected QT intervals or QTc times. For example, different sources list QTc above thresholds from 400 to 440 ms as risk factors for dangerous arrhythmia. While the common Bazett and Friderica corrections use square root and third roots in the correction factors and the Pfeufer correction depends on age and gender of the patient, the Sagie correction used in this project is basically linear:

$$QTc = QT + (1000 \text{ ms} - RR) * 0.154 \text{ (Sagie)}$$

Other resources about ECG include the websites: <https://ecglibrary.com/norm.php>, <https://ecgwaves.com/topic/ecg-normal-p-wave-qrs-complex-st-segment-t-wave-j-point/> https://www.nottingham.ac.uk/nursing/practice/resources/cardiology/function/normal_duration.php and <https://ecg.utah.edu/lesson/3>, which support the data given so far.

The ECG library site discusses a nice example of normal ECG, including the P to QRS relationships (P below $250 \mu\text{V}$ in Einthoven lead II, below 110 ms, PR between 120 and 200 ms, QRS below 120 ms etc.) and provides a quick overview about relevant deviations and their causes. Finally, the Polish P-wave Wikipedia article ('Załamek P') lists 40 to 110 ms as normal duration (typically 80 ms, at most 120 ms) and less than 250 to $300 \mu\text{V}$ as normal amplitude in Einthoven lead I and II.

Figure 2.9: Calibration signals: Scope view and analysis of a 2Hz signal generated by the Fluke PS420 simulator. Note how the analogue high-pass filter of the MAX30003 wing circuit lets the plateaus decay, which is corrected by adding a weighted signal integral in the analysis step

2.3.4 High-Pass Filter Artefact Compensation

Using an external signal generator, a built-in analogue high-pass filter of the device becomes visible as source of signal distortions. While the filter (design corner frequency 0.5 Hz, but high tolerances) is useful to remove DC components and baseline drift, it causes exponential decay of DC signal components such as non-edge parts of rectangular waves.

It is possible to compensate that by introducing some exponential growth in signal processing: Doing so for the real-time data recording would make recordings very sensitive to noise and DC components, but applying the correction after averaging (of several ECG beats, to improve signal to noise ratio) and removal of global DC offsets can work quite well.

This is combined with some heuristically biased regression analysis and correction of the ECG sections before the QRS complex to make them more consistently follow the baseline, even when biased by previous T-waves.

2.4 Embedded System Result Display

As shown in figure 2.1, the embedded system features a small colour OLED display and a bar of colour LED, so the available space for plotting results is limited. On one hand, the LED are used to show qualitative and quantitative classification results and strengths, as listed in table 2.1, while on the other hand, several visualisations of the analysis results are overlaid on the OLED display.

Note that the NeoPixel LED array, which already has been used to show live status flags during the real-time recording phase, is used with different feature assignments for the result phase. See table 2.1 for more details.

The most important plot in this project is the averaged ECG pulse shape, anchored at the QRS complex and showing P and T waves. Key time points, as detected by the morphological analysis, are marked with vertical coloured lines. Timings which lead to a-fib classification are highlighted in different colours, for example too early P-wave onsets (too long PR interval) or too long P-waves (highlighting both onset and offset). A heatmap bar above the ECG plot indicates the smoothed slope estimates used to navigate through the ECG shape during analysis. At the top right, one large and three smaller filled rectangles indicate the overall judgement (large rectangle, using similar colours as the main status LED: red, yellow, purple, or green) and individual scores (periodogram a-fib and flutter risk, P-wave height score relative to QRS and fraction of beats selected for ECG averaging).

A bar at the right indicates, from bottom to top, which of the detected QRS complexes from first to last had surrounding pulse shapes suitable for averaging. In other words, red blocks near the bottom of that bar would correspond to differing ECG shapes or artefacts early in the recording phase and the rejection of the corresponding beats for the averaging step.

Lacking screen space for a separate plot area, R/R timing plots are just overlaid in a distinctive cyan colour: From the left to the right, lines to indicate the R/R periods from start to end of the recording, scaled to have 1500ms at the top and short intervals near the bottom. In the right two thirds on the screen, a Poincaré Plot of scattered cyan dots shows the distribution of adjacent R/R times, one axis corresponding to the duration of each R/R interval and the other to the duration of the preceding R/R interval. Note that R/R distribution characteristics are not used for the classification of recordings by a-fib or atrial flutter in this project, as already explained in the introduction. Other algorithms exist which even use the R/R distribution as the only source of information.

After displaying the results for a fixed timespan, the `ecghelper` embedded software clears all recording and status buffers and returns to idle state: Screen and LED are cleared and dimmed and the next recording starts as soon as the user connects the electrode leads, or immediately, if the leads are still connected from the previous recording. Recordings end either if the leads are disconnected, an out of range event happens (system returns to idle state in both cases), or a sufficiently long ECG recording has been gathered (system analyses the new recording and shows the result display).

2.5 Linux Corpus Processing Result Presentation

In addition to the embedded `ecghelper` system for affordable, portable and low-overhead ECG recording and classification to check for atrial fibrillation and flutter, the algorithm developed for this project also is available as a `offlineecg` Linux command line tool for offline ECG corpus analysis.

Figure 2.10: Overview of the used ECG analysis plot style, based on recordings 31/2 and 33/2 of the ECG ID corpus

Using the exact same algorithm source code as the embedded firmware, this application integrates the algorithm into a different context: There are no hardware drivers for OLED, MAX30003, NeoPixels, power management or Arduino. Instead, Linux-specific code implements reading of ECG recordings (samples stored as raw binary 16-bit data array files) and writing of PCX³ images. PCX is an older graphics file format using a simple RLE (run-length encoding) compression which I had already implemented in earlier projects. Open source tools like ImageMagick (<https://imagemagick.org/>, available in most Linux distributions as precompiled package) can transform a complete batch of PCX images into more modern formats easily (using `mogrify -format png *.pcx`). This project report for example uses `offlineecg` output graphics converted to PNG (Portable Network Graphics) images and the \LaTeX typesetting system.

The graphics canvas of `offlineecg` has a size of 640×480 pixels, which provides an appropriate amount of space given the resolution and accuracy of the plots without wasting memory, CPU time or disk space for the data export. Several example plots are discussed in section 3.3.1 and figure 2.10 gives an overview of the different types of information shown in each plot. This figure is based on recordings 31/2 and 33/2 of the ECG ID corpus: See section 3.3 for the context of that corpus.

The result plots are organised as follows: At the top, there is an overview plot of the whole used part of the ECG input data, with QRS markers. At the right, three bargraphs indicate how far into the good (NSR, normal sinus rhythm) or bad (atrial fibrillation or flutter, or general arrhythmia) range the detected features for periodogram / spectrum, P-wave height and fraction of matching, average-friendly beats are, respectively. Long red bars mean clear a-fib, while long green bars mean clear normal sinus rhythm. All red bars are additionally marked with red blocks under them, to make the graphs easier to read in black and white prints.

The upper middle of the result graphics features a heat map view of the slope distribution known from the embedded firmware, but now with fewer colours and a height modulation by colour to improve readability in black and white. Likewise, three coloured boxes at the right indicate the overall classification result in a print-friendly way: A blue box with a wave symbol is shown when additional AC hum filters have been activated for the periodogram analysis step. A red minus or a green plus in the middle mark the general outcome of either a-fib (or flutter) or NSR. Clear cases of NSR get a second green box added at the right and a different hue of green for both boxes.

³ PiCture eXchange, see <http://www.martinreddy.net/gfx/2d/PCX.txt>

A large plot at the bottom shows the averaged ECG pulse shape: Coloured vertical bars (same locations and similar colours as on the OLED display in the embedded system) mark key times detected in the morphological ECG shape analysis. Timings which provide evidence for a-fib are marked in different colours, for example red or orange. Timings for the T-waves are only shown for information purposes, but are not part of the a-fib classification yet. It would be interesting to detect the presence of multiple waves around the T-wave as additional evidence in particular for atrial flutter, not to be confused with few smaller waves which can be present in that area in physiological, normal sinus rhythm ECG. Note that up to excerpt sizes of more than 1 second, the plot has exactly one pixel per sample resolution, so it would not be useful to use a canvas of larger width. Even for very low pulse rates, the plot-worthy area rarely grows longer than one second. The cut-off is selected based on QTc times.

Overlaid in the right part of the pulse shape plot area, a plot of the periodogram analysis is shown. Short periods (DC or high frequencies) are at the bottom, long periods at the top. The plot is cut off at 256 sample period and has added markers for found peaks and key durations such as the mean R/R period. Note the plots can look rather different depending on whether and which additional AC hum filter is active during the periodogram calculations. A small bar next to the plot indicates which of the beats in the analysed recording have been selected for averaging. Again to support readability of prints, non-selected beats are marked by red blocks with a vertical gap, while selected beats are marked by filled green blocks without gap.

Finally, the lower right part of the graphics shows two types of R/R plots: At the bottom, the individual R/R durations are shown from start to end of the recording, durations above 1.5 seconds being outside the plot area. At the top, a Poincaré Plot is shown, as explained in the previous section about the OLED result display. At the given geometry, the plots have R/R resolutions of 12 ms. As they are relatively low in information content, it did not feel sensible to allocate more canvas space to show them at higher resolutions. Also, as mentioned, the R/R distributions are shown for information only. They are not part of the a-fib classification algorithm, apart from checks for average R/R limits and some influence on the segmentation and averaging process ahead of the ECG shape morphological analysis.

A number of example plots can be found in the system evaluation part of this project report, directly after this section. Of course the `offlineecg` application also produces verbose textual logs, specifying all measured metrics such as the P-wave duration and amplitude and a number of other intervals and amplitudes, as well as periodogram scoring, beat selection for averaging and various other intermediate results. For each analysed file, the periodogram, amplitude and fraction of matching beat scores are logged, as well as the final classification judgement. As the offline analysis uses qualitatively different data sources than the embedded system, there also is information logged about the heuristic decisions on automatic gain adjustment and skipping of initial artefacts, which are both specific to the offline analysis only.

The logs and generated graphics, as well as the used corpora of ECG recordings, will be supplied together with the project source code digitally. This project report discusses a few corpus examples next and the appendix shows the headers, but not the implementations of the source code, to give an overview of the software architecture.

3 System Evaluation

Having created two versions of an elaborate classification system for the detection of atrial fibrillation and flutter, it is necessary to evaluate the ability of the systems to distinguish normal sinus rhythm ECG from a-fib or flutter ECG in a wide range of contexts and in the presence of common artefacts.

One version is the embedded `ecghelper` device, which has been tested using actual and simulated ECG signals connected to the actual hardware. The other version has no hardware ECG interface, but analyses pre-recorded ECG data. To evaluate that, a set of several hundred ECG recordings from corpora freely available on the internet has been downloaded and converted into the file format expected by the Linux `offlineecg` application written for this project. Using `offlineecg`, the algorithm created for this project has been applied to all recordings. Reviewing the outcomes allowed to iteratively optimise settings for various parameters of the algorithm. Section 3.3 introduces the corpora, explains their conversion and presents some individual examples, as well as discussing the overall performance.

3.1 Practical Use

Using the system to measure actual ECG is an easy way to evaluate the user interface, artefact sensitivity and classification. As no patients could be invited to participate in a study, the author was the only subject for the experiments. Dynamic range was found to be around 4000 units at gain setting 40 V/V of the MAX30003, so the project uses 80 V/V, the second highest available gain. This also inspires the automatic gain correction limits (3500 to 8000 units) of the offline ECG corpus analysis application for Linux. In both cases, the used value range is around 1/8 of the range covered with 16-bit signed integers, so even extreme asymmetries between positive and negative parts still use less than 1/4 of the maximum and most calculations can be done without having to worry about overflows in intermediate results.

One of the experiments performed relatively early in the project was comparing the MAX30003 hardware R/R detection performance to the software algorithm designed for this project (see section 2.2.1). With appropriate compensation for the different latencies of both methods, QRS complex timestamps (see figure 1.1) usually agreed within 11 ms of each other (standard deviation 9), which is quite acceptable given that the hardware detector only has a timing granularity of 8 ms in the first place. The hardware detector takes relatively long to adjust to a new ECG and it may start by detecting only every other beat for a while. Also, the auto gain of the hardware detector can make it start detecting beats in situations were only other weak, but relatively regular artefacts are present. The software QRS detection, however, starts to detect QRS complexes after a shorter warm-up phase. In part, this is due to more narrow pre-set limits for plausible strengths of signal and derived features, but it still is flexible enough to work with most settings of an ECG simulator as well, as shown in section 3.2, so it is expected to also work with a wide range of actual patients.

Testing with the author as subject also helped to find suitable thresholds for a number of parameters for the morphology based classification and, later, for the periodogram based spectral flutter and fibrillation detection, as well as optimising various aspects of the user interface. The photograph shown in figure 2.1 demonstrates the use of the device to confirm the absence of atrial fibrillation in the ECG of the author at that time. Section 2.4 explains how to interpret the display contents and LED (light emitting diode) colours.

3.2 System Evaluation Using a Patient Simulator

A number of different tests have been performed using the Fluke PS420 multi parameter simulator and ECG signal generator which already has served as signal generator for the compensation of high-

pass filter effects in the analysis of averaged ECG pulse shapes in section 2.3.4. The tests checked rejection of several types of artefacts by the project hardware and software, proper detection of normal sinus rhythm (at various heart rates, within some limits) and atrial fibrillation and flutter, as well as reactions of the system when confronted with non-standard signals from the choice of other pathological ECG rhythms and technical signals available in the PS420.

This part of the evaluation would not have been possible without the help of Prof. Dr. Michael Möller, who kindly lent the simulator to the author to perform the experiments presented in this section.

3.2.1 AC and Muscle Artefacts

Figure 3.1: Test signals: Scope view and analysis of an 80 bpm normal sinus rhythm with 60 Hz artefact, generated by the Fluke PS420 simulator. The averaging step filters out the artefact

Figure 3.2: Test signals: Scope view and analysis of an 80 bpm normal sinus rhythm with muscle artefact, generated by the Fluke PS420 simulator. The averaging step filters out the artefact, while it may look like atrial fibrillation in spectral (periodogram) analysis

The system uses two methods to reduce the impact of AC hum artefacts from main power: One is the comb notch filter frequency response of the short input FIR filter to reject signal components

around (multiples of) 50 Hz. An example of the effects of this filter has already been shown in the design part of this project report in figure 2.4.

Another important step is the averaging of multiple ECG beats to compute a single representative pulse shape waveform for one ECG beat, anchored at the QRS complex. Because averaging emphasises signal components which are phase-locked to the QRS complex, while attenuating components which are not, it is very effective for removing artefacts not related to the ECG itself. This works not only for AC hum even at frequencies not caught by the input FIR filter, but also for muscle artefacts. When processing foreign ECG data from online corpora, 60 Hz hum is frequently found, but filtering artefacts with a period of $8 \frac{1}{3}$ samples at 500 samples per second would be less trivial than filtering artefacts with exactly 10 samples period (50 Hz at 500 samples per second). Note that some online corpora from countries with 60 Hz mains originally used 360 samples per second and have been resampled using polyphase filters with phase correction to the standard 500 samples per second used throughout this project, both in the ESP32 hardware device and in the Linux command line corpus data processing application.

3.2.2 Atrial Fibrillation and Atrial Flutter

Figure 3.3: Test signals: Scope view and analysis of the first atrial fibrillation setting of the Fluke PS420 simulator. The averaged ECG shows only at least two, wide candidates for a P-wave

While atrial fibrillation and atrial flutter might have similar spectral components compared to muscle artefacts, they do originate in the heart and are part of the ECG, not artefacts introduced from outside. Because there is a direct interaction, at least two scenarios are important for analysis:

It is possible that atrial flutter creates a quite regular signal which is phase-locked to ventricular activation. In that case, averaging will pool all phase-locked atrial electrical activity which triggered a QRS complex and make the flutter waves look like P-waves in the averaged ECG. However, the regular flutter will also stay phase-locked to some degree in the surrounding time intervals, so the averaged ECG will likely show additional wave artefacts before or after the (apparent) P-wave or even before or after the T-wave. The flutter can thus be detected by checking the averaged ECG for the presences of such additional waves.

The other scenario is that atrial activities are irregular and/or not strongly phase-locked to the QRS complexes. This can be seen mainly in atrial fibrillation recordings in ECG corpora: As fibrillation waves are more chaotic and less phase-locked, they will not show up as clear peaks similar to P-waves in the averaged signal. Instead, the segment before the QRS complex could be either totally flat, maybe with some ripple, or it could have a wide, shallow hill shape. The latter can be interpreted

Figure 3.4: Test signals: Scope view and analysis of the second atrial fibrillation setting of the Fluke PS420 simulator. The averaged ECG shows several very weak and wide candidates for a P-wave, as well as additional T-wave candidates

as an effect of the probability distribution of atrial fibrillation waves and their timing relative to QRS complexes, which are more likely to be triggered when atrial impulses are present at suitable relative points in time. Instead of having multiple pseudo P-waves, analysis will find very wide or just absent P-waves in the averaged ECG in this scenario. The wide hill shape is also marked by extending far away from the QRS complex, including very high PR times.

3.2.3 Normal Sinus Rhythm

Classifying the PR time of the averaged ECG is not trivial: The PR times that are plausible depend on the heart rate. Also, the width of the individual time windows for P-wave search (before the QRS complex) and T-wave search (after the QRS complex) has to be reduced at higher heart rates. This is done by the use of R/R time controlled search exclusion zones for P-wave search. For T-wave search, a similar effect is achieved by limiting the duration of the ECG snippets used in morphology analysis relative to QTc times, which depend on the R/R period from heartbeat to heartbeat. The project uses the accurate and easy to compute Sagie formula for QTc corrections. The search zones also exclude leading descending or trailing ascending slopes when searching for P-waves or additional pseudo P-waves. This keeps parts of the previous T-wave and parts of the QRS complex from interfering with the search.

Using those steps, ECG analysis can reliably detect P-waves in normal sinus rhythms (generated by an ECG simulator) between 30 and 240 beats per minute (bpm). Higher heart rates tend to be misinterpreted by the QRS detection and/or the QRS clean-up step: Those would try to pool adjacent beats (assuming T-waves would have caused false QRS triggers) or miss too close beats as being within the likely refractory period.

While the used ECG simulator can output ECG at up to 300 bpm, it is unlikely that atrial fibrillations are the main problem of actual patients having such high heart rates during ECG recording, so the support for pulse rates above 200 bpm has not been a priority for the current project. Likewise, result plots related to R/R timings use scale limits of 1500 ms, so pulse rates below 40 bpm and gaps of more than 1500 ms between individual beats will not show up on those plots. Those, too, do not seem to be common or relevant for the analysis of normal sinus rhythm or atrial fibrillation or flutter ECG, based on experiences with the used ECG corpora.

Figure 3.5: Test signals: Scope view and analysis of atrial flutter, generated by the Fluke PS420 simulator. The averaged ECG shows only one wide elevation instead of a specific P-wave

3.2.4 Other ECG Signals

The used Fluke PS420 multi parameter and ECG simulator can generate not only normal sinus rhythm and atrial fibrillation and flutter ECG signals, but also a variety of other ECG signals and technical signals. Observations for the technical signals were that square waves are good for evaluating step responses at various points of the signal processing chain, while low frequency triangle waves get absorbed by baseline filters (2 Hz almost completely, 2.5 Hz already gets attenuated significantly). Sine waves are good for testing frequency response: 0.5 Hz and 40 and 60 Hz get reduced by one third, while 5 and 10 Hz show at high amplitude. Sine waves of 50 and 100 Hz are recorded more than 20 times weaker than 40 Hz waves.

Testing with normal sinus rhythm ECG signals, the spectral evaluation score based on periodogram peaks varies somewhat by heart rate: This should be compensated by improved scoring before this score is given more weight in classification compared to the morphology evaluation, which provides more important data for the current classifier. As mentioned, analysis and QRS based segmentation does not work properly for heart rates of 260, 280 and 300 bpm (the highest rates available in the simulator). Those are either rejected as too noisy (no atrial fibrillation detection possible) or, in the 300 bpm case, classified as atrial fibrillation. The latter is due to every second beat being detected, so the analysis of the assumed 150 bpm signal finds too many ECG waves in the averaged pulse shape.

The system does avoid interference by any of the simulated artefacts of the PS420: Both 50 and 60 Hz AC hum are removed by either the input FIR filter or the averaging, which also removes muscle artefacts. Baseline wander and breathing artefacts already are absorbed by the analogue high-pass filter of the hardware anyway. The very regular simulated muscle artefacts classify as potential atrial fibrillation in the periodogram spectral analysis: While there is no override of this classification by the very clean averaged ECG shape as judged by the morphological analysis, muscle artefacts will be mistaken as atrial fibrillation. This problem is not addressed in the current version of the project.

Pacemaker rhythms can also be classified as atrial fibrillation by the current project algorithm, as there will be no P-waves of the expected type, just short impulses which may vanish in averaging due to limited phase locking precision. Demand pacing will be analysed as normal while there is a sufficiently high fraction of normal sinus rhythm beats, as are PVC (premature ventricular contractions) and PAC (atrial), as long as there are not too many of them in a recording.

Figure 3.6: Test signals: Analysis of 30 and 220 bpm normal sinus rhythms generated by the Fluke PS420 simulator. The search scopes for P- and T-waves adapt to the different average R/R timespans

Bursts of 11 PVC can trigger a-fib classification, as they can form a majority of the recorded beats and the averaged waveform will become PVC, not NSR (normal sinus rhythm), but bursts of 5 PVC just get sorted out in the automated selection of snippets for ECG averaging step. Likewise, trigeminy with every third beat being PVC gets sorted out, classifying the remaining beats as NSR, while bigeminy (every second beat PVC) does not, classifying the recording as a-fib. This could be avoided in the future by improving the snippet selection heuristics. Not surprisingly, the classification for ventricular tachycardia (purely PVC) is a-fib, as the ECG shape is not NSR and the algorithm does not distinguish between different deviations from NSR in the sense necessary to be able to recognise PVC as such. This does not seem problematic given the project context, as the absence of NSR always justifies further investigations even if neither a-fib nor atrial flutter are present.

Supraventricular tachycardia for example also gets classified as a-fib by the algorithm, as the ECG shows just QRS and T at high rate, no P, while atrial tachycardia can get classified as a-fib based on P timing. On the other hand, sinus arrhythmia and nodal rhythm are classified as normal by the current algorithm: The R/R are chaotic or slow, but there are P-waves at the expected times. Right and Left Bundle Branch Block only affect ST and T morphology, so the former gets classified as normal while the latter is classified as a-fib due to T-P interactions. Heart blocks all are classified as a-fib, because the P-waves are far ahead of the QRS complexes and are not detected in the expected time window. The algorithm interprets the absence of normal timed P-waves as cases of atrial fibrillation or flutter.

3.3 ECG Corpus Analysis

To adapt the algorithm to a broad spectrum of actual ECG data, a range of corpora freely available on the internet has been downloaded and converted to a fixed 500 sps, 16-bit binary format for processing by the Linux `offlineecg` tool written for this project. Several of the corpora are part of PhysioNet ([Goldberger]). Using the corpora, it was possible to manually optimise settings for a number of parameters in the algorithm. A future project could use machine learning here: There are a number of large ECG corpora available which have not yet been explored in the current project. In general, long-term recordings at low sampling rates such as 128 sps did not seem appropriate for morphology analysis, having a rather coarse time resolution.

The largest corpus with 310 recordings of 20 seconds each, measured at 12-bit resolution (± 10 mV) and 500 sps is the ECG ID corpus [Lugovaya] created by Tatiana Lugovaya to design an algorithm for biometric identification based on ECG. Of the 310 recordings, three (47/02, 76/02, 88/01) were originally excluded from `offlineecg` analysis because they contain large amplitude artefacts. Shifting and clipping amplitudes to the range of signed 12-bit integers allowed to use the full set of recordings nevertheless. The files represent a pool of 90 persons, most with 2, some with up to 20 recordings per person. It is expected that few of them exhibit atrial fibrillation or arrhythmia. The recordings are available in two channels, one unfiltered and one with band-pass filter and noise reduction. This project uses the unfiltered Einthoven lead I data to match the natural context of the hardware.

The second largest corpus used for this project is the TELE ECG Database [Khamis] which contains 250 telehealth recordings made using handheld Ag/AgCl plate electrodes and the 12-bit, 500 sps TeleMedCare Health Monitor. Apart from the lower resolution, the recordings give a good impression of the expected quality of ECG recorded by the `ecghelper` embedded system, which uses dry wristband electrodes and the same sampling rate and almost the same Einthoven lead I recording setup. The database demonstrates the robustness of a QRS detection algorithm, providing 250 recordings of at least 20 seconds each. 29 of the recordings originate from manual selection of explicitly poor recordings, the others are a random sample.

As the database came in CSV (comma separated values) text floating point format, it had to be converted back to integer values. Contrary to the documentation, three files used a different quantization step (0.002773 mV in recordings 82/99, 83/100 and 84/101), the others use step size 0.002713 mV as documented. To determine step size, differences between sorted amplitudes were used: Step size is max of differences divided by `round(maximum of differences / minimum of differences)`.

In addition, based on manual inspection of analysis results, 39 of the recordings seem to have swapped leads. To compensate for this, `offlineecg` now checks for the magic file name pattern `_INV` before the file name extension and sign-swaps the sample data when the pattern is found. Lead-swapped files have been manually tagged as such by renaming them to `oldname_INV.eric`, which affects the recordings 1/1, 2/2, 3/3, 7/7, 8/8, 9/9, 40/53, 46/59, 47/60, 48/61, 49/62, 50/63, 51/64, 62/75, 63/77, 64/78, 85/102, 86/103, 87/104, 108/130, 109/131, 110/132, 111/135, 112/136, 113/137, 114/138, 115/139, 116/140, 138/164, 171/199, 173/201, 198/226, 199/227, 201/229, 211/240, 212/241, 213/242, 232/266, and 243/290.

The third corpus is the Heterogeneous Dataset of Arrhythmia [Medhi], with 150 selected excerpts from the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia database (which can be found on PhysioNet, but is too large to be used in scope of this project). Each of the 150 files is 10 seconds short and available in 360 sps Matlab data files at 12-bit effective resolution. The recordings polyphase resampled by 25/18, using Octave resample and the signal package, to 500 sps and recording 1/212 has been tagged as lead-swapped. Recordings 1/172 and 1/183 have been excluded for containing too short ECG recordings, starting with longer artefacts. In addition, the download also contained 8 sets of 4 recordings each from the Intracardial A-Fib Database discussed next. Of those, 6 sets containing lead I data have been used as a separate corpus of 24 files: They are short 10 second excerpts from the same ECG as the Intracardial A-Fib Database.

The Intracardiac Atrial Fibrillation Database [Peterson] contains 4 recordings each from 8 patients, sampled at 1000 sps and 14-bit resolution using 8 channels in a 16-bit binary format. Of those, 24 files (the data for 6 patients) contain lead I data which is used for this project. Octave decimate (with Chebyshev type 1 order 8 low-pass) has been used to resample the recordings to 500 sps. The polarity of recording IAF4 IVC seems ambiguous.

The last used corpus are the 23 recordings from [Moody], a paper about detecting a-fib using R/R intervals. Which is a common approach, but very different from the approach used in this project.

The recordings are very long 250sps, 12-bit resolution files stored in a packed binary format where 3 bytes contain one sample for two channels: Einthoven lead I and II. The former is used for this project, after upsampling (using Octave interp and the signal package, 17 tap FIR) to 500sps. As the embedded `ecghelper` always works with short recordings, short 4 minute excerpts (offset 4 hours from the start of each ≥ 10 hour corpus recording) were used for `offlineecg` analysis, to make the corpus task more similar to the embedded task. This gives the `offlineecg` heuristics some room to skip part of the data and select a 30 second subset best suited for analysis. The AFDB also contains two additional recordings, 03665 and 00735, which lack lead I data and have not been used for this project. File 08434 has been manually tagged as a probable lead-swap.

3.3.1 Example ECG Fragment Analyses

Figure 3.7: Left: A-Fib corpora recording 3/17: Irregular R/R periods, flutter most visible in averaged T-wave, less in P-wave, strong spectral components. Classified as a-fib by spectrum. Right: A-Fib corpora recording 3/19: Several shallow candidate P-wave shapes in averaged pulse shape caused by flutter, also extra waves around T-wave

Figure 3.8: Left: A-Fib corpora recording 3/29: Alternating R/R periods, P-wave vanishes by averaging across beats. Right: ECG ID corpus recording 01/20: Could be normal sinus rhythm with wave, noise or muscle artefacts, small waves even in averaged pulse shape, but still clearly visible P-wave

This section shows a selection of ECG analysis graphs generated by the `offlineecg` tool using the algorithm developed for this project. Most of the figures show examples from atrial fibrillation corpora, as the detection of normal sinus rhythm seemed to be a relatively easy task based on

Figure 3.9: Left: A-Fib corpora recording IAF3 SVC: Longer recording shows high R/R Poincare plot dispersion, no discernible P-wave in averaged pulse shape. Right: A-Fib corpora recording 08455: No P-wave in averaged pulse shape, high R/R Poincare plot dispersion

Figure 3.10: Left: A-Fib corpora recording 08219: Strong flutter waves with few, large peaks in periodogram spectral analysis, two P-wave candidates in averaged pulse shape due to phase-locked QRS complexes. A-fib detected via spectrum. Right: A-Fib corpora recording 04746: Spectrum lacks a-fib signs, but P-wave absent in averaged pulse shape and high R/R Poincare plot dispersion. Grey area excluded from P-wave search at high heart rate

experiments with the PS420 patient simulator and ECG signal generator. So instead, selected cases of a-fib are presented here, together with explanations of which aspects of those recordings give most evidence of a-fib to the algorithm.

Figure 3.7 shows two clear cases of atrial flutter: One of them accordingly has a high periodogram score based on strong autocorrelation peaks for shift 129 and weaker peaks for shifts 87, 169 and 216 samples while the mean R/R is 533 samples (2 ms per sample). So there is a strong 3.9 Hz periodicity in this ECG, while the average pulse rate is only 56 bpm. The automatically activated 60 Hz hum filter causes a smooth periodogram with clear peaks, as well as higher CPU usage. The other example has weak 60 Hz hum, so the filter is not used, but still a peak around 3.9 Hz (127 samples) and several smaller peaks are detected, already giving rise to a mediocre periodogram score. The actual classification as a-fib, however, is triggered here by the presence of two P-wave like shapes of similar amplitude: In the left case, there was still a large difference between amplitudes, making the flutter interpretation of the waves in the averaged ECG less clear.

The next two examples in figure 3.8 show one of the common R/R symptoms in atrial flutter in the left plot: Alternating between QRS complexes after either 2 or 3 flaps of the atrial flutter. While

there is no Poincaré Plot analysis in the algorithm of this project (it could detect that there are 2 or more clusters in the scatterplot), the approach of averaging ECG over multiple beats also works: There is not one clear P location ahead of all QRS complexes, so the averaged P wave is stretched out and shallow, both triggers for the algorithm to classify the ECG as a-fib. The right plot, taken from the ECG ID corpus, shows a normal sinus rhythm recorded with strong noise in the recording. The noise is clearly distinguishable from a-fib or atrial flutter in the periodogram and the averaged ECG pulse shape does reveal a clear P-wave by improving signal to noise ratio by averaging. So while the recording looks suspicious at casual inspection, the algorithm easily recognises it as normal sinus rhythm.

Figure 3.9 shows two obvious cases of atrial fibrillation: While atrial flutter tends to exhibit extra waves in averaged ECG shapes, a-fib instead can be recognised by the total absence of P-waves of significant height in the averaged ECG. Poincaré Plot based methods would have instead used the unusually high dispersion of the scatterplot as sign of probable a-fib: The pulse is very irregular.

Two more cases are shown in figure 3.10: First, there are again strong spectral components in the periodogram of the left recording. It does seem to have a P-wave in averaging, which can be caused by phase-locking between irregular subsets of the atrial impulses triggering QRS reactions with a fixed time course relative to the atrial impulse. There is not enough evidence for extra waves in the averaged ECG, though, which also ends too early to investigate extra waves around T-waves. At the right, P-waves are absent in the averaged ECG. The shaded area marks a search scope exclusion caused by the high average pulse rate, to avoid counting previous T-waves as possible P-waves. Strong spectral or periodogram components are 6.2, 17.2, 4.5 and 9.6 Hz sorted by descending strength for the left and 6.4 and 3.1 Hz for the right recording.

Finally, figure 3.11 shows the two cases where recordings from the a-fib recordings have not been classified as a-fib: The left recording has an unusual QRS complex shape, causing a failure to distinguish the different waves properly. The algorithm seems to have taken the very small R wave as Q and a hill around the Q wave as P-wave.

Figure 3.11: Left: A-Fib corpora recording IAF4 SVC: Not detected as a-fib after failed automated classification of P-wave geometry near unusually shaped QRS complex. Right: A-Fib corpora recording 05261: Not detected as a-fib, while strength of a-fib seems to vary over time in the full length ECG plot at the top

The recording on the right side is probably a correct detection of a period without a-fib in one of the recordings in one of the a-fib corpora. There are some irregularities in the second half of the segment, but on average, the recording does not exhibit clear atrial fibrillation nor flutter. The periodogram score, too, shows some signs of pathological atrial activity, but those are not strong enough to warrant classification of the recording as a-fib.

3.3.2 Overall ECG Corpus Analysis Performance

Table 3.1 presents the overall outcome of applying the algorithm developed for this project to all 781 ECG recordings. Of all 71 files in the explicit atrial fibrillation corpora, three were not classified as a-fib: Heterogeneous A-Fib 3/16 (classified as noisy), AFDB 05261 (classified as normal sinus rhythm) and intracardial AFDB file IAF4 SVC (also classified as normal sinus rhythm). File 3/16 contains only 6 QRS complexes in a short 10 second recording: The algorithm finds the last 5 of them, using the start to adjust thresholds, but one of the 4 remaining beats is ectopic and most R/R intervals are > 1.6 seconds. Files 05261 and IAF4 SVC have already been discussed above: The former seems to be a mostly normal sinus rhythm phase of the used long-term recording and the latter is hard to classify for the algorithm because of the unusual QRS shape.

Count	Class	Rate	Corpus / Amplitude Resolution / Format
1	GOOD	250 sps	Atrial Fibrillation Database, 12-bit, packed binary
22	BAD	250 sps	Atrial Fibrillation Database, 12-bit, packed binary
1	GOOD	1000 sps	Intracardial A-Fib Database, 14-bit, binary
23	BAD	1000 sps	Intracardial A-Fib Database, 14-bit, binary
23	BAD	1000 sps	A-Fib from Heterogeneous Dataset... , 14-bit, Matlab
1	NOISY	1000 sps	A-Fib from Heterogeneous Dataset... , 14-bit, Matlab
32	GOOD	360 sps	Heterogeneous Dataset of Arrhythmia, 12-bit, Matlab
24	OKAY	360 sps	Heterogeneous Dataset of Arrhythmia, 12-bit, Matlab
86	BAD	360 sps	Heterogeneous Dataset of Arrhythmia, 12-bit, Matlab
8	NOISY	360 sps	Heterogeneous Dataset of Arrhythmia, 12-bit, Matlab
67	GOOD	500 sps	Telehealth Corpus, (re-quantified) 12-bit, CSV
39	OKAY	500 sps	Telehealth Corpus, (re-quantified) 12-bit, CSV
143	BAD	500 sps	Telehealth Corpus, (re-quantified) 12-bit, CSV
1	NOISY	500 sps	Telehealth Corpus, (re-quantified) 12-bit, CSV
217	GOOD	500 sps	ECG ID Corpus, 12-bit, binary
63	OKAY	500 sps	ECG ID Corpus, 12-bit, binary
30	BAD	500 sps	ECG ID Corpus, 12-bit, binary

Table 3.1: Classification result counts for the 6 evaluated ECG corpora, using the `offlineecg` tool written for this project. Classification and graphical and textual result output took 12 seconds for a total of 781 fragments, not counting the separate conversion step from PCX (PiCture eXchange) to PNG (Portable Network Graphics). All corpora have been resampled to 500 sps for analysis, which always used lead I data (some corpora contain data for several leads)

The algorithm performs well for the small a-fib corpora, two of which are even different length excerpts from the same data. How well does it perform for larger, more heterogeneous corpora? Of the 150 files in the Heterogeneous Dataset of Arrhythmia (not counting the 1000 sps subset of explicit a-fib recordings discussed above), 8 are classified as too noisy or artefact-rich to decide, 86 as probable a-fib and 32 plus 24 as good or at least okay examples of normal sinus rhythm. As tachycardia may not classify as a-fib and limited amounts of ectopic or premature beats get sorted out in the averaging step, there is indeed limited support for classification of recordings containing other types of arrhythmia than atrial fibrillation or flutter.

Metadata excerpts for all recordings which were not classified as a-fib or noisy in this corpus can be found in the `evaluation.tex` file of this project report. Only two files in this group explicitly mention a-fib or flutter in the metadata and must be considered failed detections: 1/29 and 1/135. In total, 24 files mention a-fib or flutter in the metadata, so 22 of them were correctly detected by the algorithm, while many files with other arrhythmia also triggered the algorithm. As expected, the algorithm is good at distinguishing NSR from a-fib, but not designed to distinguish NSR or a-fib from certain other pathological ECG patterns. The two possible missed instances of a-fib are

Figure 3.12: Left: Telehealth recording 1/29: Not detected as a-fib, but metadata lists a-fib at 33 minutes into the recording. Elevated periodogram score might be related to that. Right: Telehealth recording 1/135, not detected as a-fib, while metadata lists atrial fibrillation. The analysed start of the recording does not seem to contain a-fib.

shown in figure 3.12, it seems plausible that the analysed time segments itself indeed are free from clear a-fib waves in the ECG.

Being a test corpus for QRS detection, the Telehealth Corpus does not include metadata annotation which would specify whether or not a given file contains a-fib or atrial flutter. According to the algorithm developed for this project, 1 file is too noisy to decide, 143 do contain a-fib or atrial flutter, while 106 do not (67 of them more certainly than the others).

As the corpus has been collected in a telemedicine context, it is plausible that a large part of the recordings does contain a-fib, atrial flutter or other arrhythmia which the algorithm is not designed to specifically distinguish from either normal sinus rhythm or a-fib.

A cardiologist could review all ECG recordings and create a reference list of judgements as a gold standard for the a-fib classification task in a future project. At first glance, the algorithm might have missed more cases of extra waves in the averaged ECG than it has falsely rejected normal rhythms, while agreeing with the impression of the author for most recordings. However, the lack of T-wave analysis or search for extra waves around the T-wave is a missed opportunity for more informed classifications: Atrial flutter waves can be visible in averaged ECG as extra waves spread over the entire time axis, not just close to the actual or artefact P-wave.

Finally, the results for the ECG ID corpus are 280 recordings classified as normal sinus rhythm (217 of them with high confidence) and 30 classified as a-fib or atrial flutter. Having more than 10 percent of a-fib incidence in a sample of the normal population in a corpus made for biometric human recognition seems high. The recordings classified as a-fib are: 01/11, 01/15, 05/01, 05/02, 07/01, 13/02, 14/02, 20/02, 22/01, 24/05, 30/01, 30/02, 30/03, 30/04, 30/05, 47/02, 63/03, 63/04, 63/05, 70/03, 72/05, 73/01, 73/02, 74/01, 76/02, 79/02, 87/02, 88/01, 89/01, and 89/02.

Looking at the grouping of the files by subject, this means that for 4 subjects, the algorithm has classified all recordings as a-fib, for 2 additional subjects it has classified 3 out of 6, or 2 out of 20 available recordings as a-fib and for further 14 subjects, it classified only 1 of 2 or more recordings as a-fib.

If one assumes that the algorithm was pessimistic about ECG at current settings, a recommendation to the users could be to take the `ecghelper` test again when the classifier detects possible a-fib: Only when both test runs suggest that the patient does experience an episode of a-fib at the time of testing, a-fib probability should be considered to be high.

Using those instructions, the `ecghelper` system does suggest for 5 or 6 out of 90 participants (7.7 percent) of the ECG ID corpus to have their ECG checked for possible atrial fibrillation or atrial flutter.

Inspecting those cases manually yields the following results: Some P-waves for person 1 have a smooth and wide base, the algorithm classifies them as too long with the current onset / offset search parameters. Persons 5, 63, 73 and to some degree person 1 have very wavy averaged ECG shapes, which can be evidence for atrial flutter, too noisy too short recordings or for muscle artefacts.

Person 73 might additionally exhibit a 2-peaked P-wave, which can occur in atrial abnormalities according to <http://www.metealpaslan.com/ecg/laaen.htm> and is a risk factor for atrial fibrillation according to the same website. Person 89 has no Q-wave detectable by the algorithm, which causes a failure of Q peak and Q onset detection which limits the search range for P-waves, in turn leading to classification of the ECG as a-fib because the remaining P-wave is small. By judgement of the author, 5 out of the 6 persons suspected by the algorithm to have atrial fibrillations do indeed exhibit signs of a-fib or atrial flutter in their averaged ECG pulse shape.

4 Conclusions

The algorithms developed for this project have proven to be able to distinguish most cases of atrial fibrillation and atrial flutter from normal sinus rhythm ECG, even in the presence of common artefacts, on an affordable embedded platform consisting of an ESP32 board with a MAX30003 ECG analogue front-end board as pluggable peripheral extension and a bar of NeoPixel colour LED (light emitting diode) and a small colour OLED (organic LED) display. All parts, including a set of reusable dry wrist / limb electrodes, are available online and no soldering or manufacturing of components was required to create the proof of concept hardware platform.

Having designed the algorithm in a way which keeps CPU load low and uses only integer arithmetics, the `ecghelper` firmware only uses ten percent of the performance available on the CPU of the ESP32 system on a chip.

Classification can succeed with as little as 10 seconds of 500 sps of ECG data and with low dynamic ranges of a few 1000 ADC (analogue digital converter) quantization units on hardware and even less in many of the ECG corpus data used to test the algorithm. Using up to 30 seconds of recorded data, the embedded system takes only one second to analyse the recording and present a classification result and a comprehensive overview of the metrics, pulse morphology analysis and periodogram leading to that classification. More than 60 kB of working memory are used for that: Shorter recordings can be classified using less memory and a trade-off between analysis speed and memory usage is possible at the periodogram stage.

At the lower end of the range of usable platforms might be 32-bit microcontrollers with a few dozen kilobytes of working memory and a built-in ADC for a few USD at volume prices, with a discrete analogue front-end using entry level instrumentation amplifiers. For comparison, the core chips of the current hardware, an ESP32 best bought as WROOM32 integrated module and the MAX30003 biopotential / ECG analogue front-end, are around 15 € together even at small quantities.

Running the same algorithm on a standard desktop PC allows classification of thousands of ECG fragments between 10 and 30 seconds per minute, even without using multiple threads or cores. The CPU load is dominated by the periodogram generation in that case, followed by the generation of PCX (PiCture eXchange) graphics files with the classification results and the corresponding I/O. Using different algorithms for the spectral judgement, such as FFT, or periodogram estimation from a subset of the recording, could speed up desktop processing even further. The test corpora of 781 fragments are classified in a minute even now, counting image conversion to PNG (portable network graphics) file format as part of that time.

4.1 System Performance

While the project algorithm is a good match for the available embedded hardware performance, allowing classification of ECG after a reasonably short recording phase (up to 30 seconds) and waiting phase (1 second), the important question is of course how good the algorithm is at making correct decisions. Pooling information from the dedicated a-fib corpora used for testing and a-fib metadata annotation from the heterogeneous arrhythmia corpus, the algorithm claims that 4 files out of 93 do not contain a-fib and one additional file is too noisy to decide. Half of those 4 indeed seem to contain little a-fib during the short excerpts analysed by the algorithm based on manual inspection presented in the evaluation section of this project report. One can conclude that the algorithm rarely fails to detect significant a-fib or flutter activity.

On the other hand, while the algorithm detects some evidence of a-fib for 20 out of 90 participants in a corpus for ECG biometry, it only does so across two or more recordings for 6 of them, 5 of whom indeed show signs of possible a-fib based on manual inspection of the data. This leads to the

recommendation to repeat the measurement when the embedded system shows an a-fib classification of the current ECG, to reduce the risk of false positives.

Based on experience with the other corpora, the high incidence of a-fib classifications in the tele-health corpus probably does reflect an actual bias of people being more likely to have their ECG recorded and reviewed while they do experience arrhythmia such as atrial fibrillation.

4.2 Future Work

To optimise and evaluate the algorithm further, it can be applied to a larger set of recordings. When gold standard classifications are available in the metadata, or can be provided by cooperation with a cardiologist, machine learning can be used to optimise algorithm parameter settings.

Both the morphology analysis and in particular the spectral analysis can be improved by that approach. In addition, the morphology stage could be extended by spotting extra (flutter) waves around the T-wave and using heuristics to distinguish wavy from noisy average ECG pulse shapes. The spectral analysis could explore for example FFT or Fast Hartley Transform.

In cooperation with a cardiologist, a study where an actual group of patients uses the device would be possible, for example comparing the classification by the device to results from using a medical ECG system right before or after the device, or comparing the algorithmic decision to the known health status of the patients.

In context of previous projects of the author and the professional experience of the cardiologist discussed in the introduction, another very interesting future task would be the design of a more integrated device, as described in section 1.4. This would involve the design of a small circuit board for the MAX30003 (largest version is pitch 0.5 mm TQFN-28 thin quad flat no-leads package), the WROOM32 module (1.27 mm pitch), power and USB (Universal Serial Bus) bridge, some colour LED and a header for a small OLED or IPS TFT LCD display. Integrating some form of audible feedback would improve usability.

A combination of all three aspects would make up an exciting challenge for example for a M.Sc. thesis: Improve algorithm and parameters using machine learning, then port the improvements to the current embedded platform. Design and build a customised version of the hardware and use the optimised product in a small study with actual patients.

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Websites mentioned in the text have been checked for validity in July 2020.

Appendix

A Appendix: Hardware

Figure A.1: HUZZAH32 ESP32 feather board with stacking headers, source: adafruit.com

A.1 ESP32 HUZZAH32 Feather Board

The core of the device used in this project is a HUZZAH32 ESP32 feather board with stacking headers: It has pins at the bottom to plug it into a standard breadboard and sockets on top which can be used to stack other boards on top of it. There is a Li-Ion / Li-Poly battery header, but for simplicity, the board was either powered through USB (Universal Serial Bus) from a PC, which also provides connectivity for programming and debugging, or a power bank which provides power over USB, to avoid ground loops. This reduces AC artefacts in the ECG and it is safer for patients.

The core of the HUZZAH32 is a small ESP32-WROOM-32 module which contains the ESP32 system on a chip and the necessary antenna for Bluetooth and WLAN (wireless LAN, network) connectivity. The HUZZAH32, shown in figure A.1 (from adafruit.com, used with permission), contains a battery controller, voltage regulator (peak load 500 mA, continuous load should be lower to reduce heat) and USB serial converter for easy in-circuit programming (ICP) and debugging.

A number of additional ESP32 features are not used in the project: Hall sensor, capacitive touch interface, 2 DAC (digital analogue converter) and ADC (analogue digital converter) on most GPIO (general purpose input output), additional UART (serial I/O) and SPI (serial peripheral interconnect) channels, I2C (serial I/O), I2S (serial audio I/O), PWM (pulse-width modulation), SDIO (SD input output) and SD (secure digital) memory card interface. Refer to the ESP32 documentation for more information about those, for example the WROOM32 data sheet https://www.espressif.com/sites/default/files/documentation/esp32-wroom-32_datasheet_en.pdf. It is possible to connect external flash or RAM (random access memory) via SPI or SDIO, but the built-in 4 MB flash and 520 kB RAM were more than enough for the project firmware.

In addition, there are a reset button, a single software controlled red LED (Light Emitting Diode) and an orange LED to indicate battery charger status) on the module. The project does not require either, as the application runs in an endless loop after power up and the serial USB ICP can force a reset over USB. User interface and output use external LED (see section A.3) and a display:

The breadboard connectivity has proven to be convenient for attaching a small colour OLED (organic LED) display: Apart from 3.3V power and ground, this needs the following digital signals: Reset (connected to reset of the HUZAZH32), clock, data, data/command selection (D/nC) and select. Data and clock support unidirectional SPI, the display only receives commands and data in SPI mode. The OLED has no SPI return channel, but the software reserves a return data GPIO.

A.2 MAX30003WING ECG Analog Front-End Board

Figure A.2: Maxim MAX30003WING board and pinout, own photo with annotations

Being designed specifically for the feather / wing form factor, the MAX30003WING plugs directly on top of the HUZAZH32, which makes all necessary connections between ESP32 and MAX30003. In addition, the wing has a 3.5 mm socket (headphone socket style) to connect ECG electrodes. Suitable wrist band electrode kits, as well as cables for connecting discardable stick-on ECG electrodes for more professional measurements, are available from Olimex and other vendors.

The MAX30003 ECG analogue front-end features 500 M Ω input impedances, sampling rates of 125, 128, 199.8, 200, 250, 256, 500 and 512 samples per second (this project uses 500, which is a multiple of 50 Hz AC mains frequency and allows fine timing resolution measurements) and up to 65 mV peak-peak AC, ± 650 mV DC offsets input range. Depending on selected gain, up to 15.5 effective bits of ADC resolution can be used. Internally, the chip decimates 18 bit samples taken at suitable rates around 32 kHz. The chip uses a PLL (phase-locked loop) to derive clocks from an external 32768 Hz reference clock and implements optional digital filtering: Available 12-tap FIR low-pass filter cut-off frequency options include 40, 100 and 150 Hz at 500 samples per second (28 at the lowest rates, 40 and 100 Hz at medium and slightly higher frequencies at power of two rates).

Recommended for this project are 40 or 100 Hz. The chip also has built-in ESD (electro-static discharge) protection and a calibration signal and reference voltage generator. SPI communication clocks up to 12 MHz are supported. Depending on filters and sampling rate, latencies from electrode terminals to digital recording are between 20 and 153 ms. Samples are stored in a 32 word FIFO (first in, first out memory buffer), which makes data collection easy and less time critical. FIFO packets are tagged with flag bits to indicate when to stop reading or to mark drift recovery artefacts.

On-chip IIR (first order Butterworth) high-pass filtering at 0.5 Hz is not recommended for this project, as the used MAX30003WING board already connects a 1 μ F capacitor to the analogue high-pass circuit of the MAX30003 to configure that to nominally 0.44 Hz cut-off frequency. Using a 100 nF capacitor as C2 for 10 times lower cut-off frequency would help to reduce phase distortion, which could occur for signal components of up to 2 to 5 Hz with the current circuit, at the cost of being less effective against baseline wander. The MAX30003 IIR filter or software baseline drift correction, both currently disabled, could then be used to compensate reduced analogue filtering.

The MAX30003 also features built-in, Pan/Tompkins inspired hardware QRS complex R/R detection at 8 ms time granularity with up to 106 ms latency: The project only signals detected events, but does not use the detections for ECG analysis. Various parameters of the hardware R/R detection are configurable in the driver. More useful features in context of this project are the automated very low power lead-on and lead-off detection, which injects tiny (configurable, 5 to 100 nA) currents at the electrode terminals and checks the resulting electrode voltages, as well as automated and manual recovery from high DC offsets by dynamically modulating high-pass filters.

At the moment, the lead detection is only used to automatically start measurements when the user connects the electrodes and abort them when contact is lost, but suitable programming would allow the ESP32 to wait in hibernate state and boot as soon as measurements start. That way, the device could be ready to wake up for measurements for a long time even with battery power.

By lucky coincidence, the wing also has two 4-pin Grove connectors and a PMOD⁴ connector for peripherals. The Grove connectors have two data pins, 3.3 V and ground each, as shown in figure A.2. One connector is intended for I2C bus (with SDA data and SCL clock), the other for serial communications (with TX and RX data), but as most pins of the ESP32 are versatile in their GPIO (general-purpose input output) use, there was no problem to use the serial Grove connector RX pin for the pulse width modulated serial LED data of an array of 15 NeoPixel colour LED.

A.3 NeoPixel Colour LED Bar

The WS2813 NeoPixel colour LED contain shift registers and a controller for pulse width brightness modulation: The R, G and B channel can each be set to any of 256 different brightness levels between off and full 20 mA on by sending a pulse width (phase) encoded packet of 24 bit length. Chains of multiple LED simply are programmed by sending longer packets to the resulting longer shift register of the cascaded LED.

⁴Peripheral module interface, a connector standard, see http://digilentinc.com/Pmods/Digilent-Pmod_%20Interface_Specification.pdf

Figure A.3: Seed Studio NeoPixel colour LED bar pinout, source: seedstudio.com, CC-BY-SA

Here, one bar of 15 NeoPixel is connected to the serial Grove connector of the MAX30003WING, using the RX pin for LED data. Pin assignments are shown in figures A.2 and A.3. The latter is used here under the Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike 4.0 international license according to <https://wiki.seeedstudio.com/license/>. The Grove connector also provides the NeoPixels with 3.3 V, so MAX30003WING, OLED and NeoPixels all share the HUZAZH32 power supply.

However, as each NeoPixel LED draws 60mA at full brightness, the HUZAZH32 voltage regulator can only handle very few of them, in particular while sending wireless data or during other high power activities of the ESP32. The NeoPixel are extremely bright at full power, so the project firmware simply limits the range of brightness values to 0 to 31 instead of 0 to 255, thereby limiting current draw to at most 112 mA instead of 900 mA for the whole array of 15 NeoPixels.

Alternatively, it would have been possible to divert the power pin of the NeoPixel bar to a separate voltage regulator, but nominally, USB 2.0 power is limited to 500 mA anyway. Also, the project firmware only uses 4 of the 15 LED for normal operations and 4 more for enhanced classification feedback. Seed Studio sells bars of 10, 15 and 25 and rings of 16, 24 and 42 pixels.

A.4 Pin Assignment Overview

While figure A.2 shows the pin assignments of the wing, a number of other pins of the feather are used in this project. Numbering the pins from the top (USB connector on the feather, PMOD connector on the wing) to the bottom (ECG electrode connector on the wing, WROOM32 module with antenna on the feather) the pinout of the feather (shown in figure A.4, from adafruit.com, used with permission) is as follows:

Left: 1 reset (input and output, connect to OLED reset), 2 3.3 V (to OLED), 3 n.c. (no connection), 4 ground (to OLED), 5 GPIO26 (OLED SPI data), 6 GPIO25 (OLED SPI clock), 7 (GPIO34, input-only!), 8 (GPIO39, input-only!), 9 (GPIO36, input-only!), 10 GPIO4 (to OLED D/nC), 11 GPIO5/SCK (MAX30003 SPI clock), 12 GPIO18/MOSI (data to MAX30003 SPI), 13 GPIO19/MISO (data from MAX30003 SPI), 14 GPIO16/RX (data to NeoPixels), 15 GPIO17/TX (to OLED nCS) and 16 GPIO21 (connected to GND via MAX30003 board). GPIO34 is reserved for return data from the OLED in `ecghelper`, but not used for the current display.

Right: 1 (battery), 2 (en, pull down to power off ESP32), 3 (5 V from USB, can connect voltage regulators for additional peripherals here), 4 GPIO13 and connected to red on-board LED of the feather, 5 (GPIO12 and special role during reset), 6 GPIO27 (can connect to second MAX30003 interrupt line via optional jumper), 7 GPIO33 (to MAX30003 interrupt line), 8 GPIO15 (to MAX30003 nCS), 9 (GPIO32), 10 (GPIO14), 11 (GPIO22/SCL, to I2C Grove header), 12 (GPIO23/SDA, to

Figure A.4: Pinout of the HUZZAH32 ESP32 feather board, source: adafruit.com

I2C Grove header). Note that I2C bus use would require adding pull-up resistors for SCL and SDA. A $10\text{ k}\Omega$ resistor between the battery pin and ground gives the charge controller a sink for the 4.15 V charge voltage, so the yellow HUZZAH32 charge status LED stops flickering and stays on steadily.

A.5 Amplitude Calibration

The MAX30003 has a built-in calibration signal source, which can generate mono- and bipolar rectangular waves with selectable duty cycles and a defined amplitude. By using this signal instead of the external ECG leads as source, it is possible to evaluate the actual ADC gain and all distortions introduced between ADC input and analysed ECG wave. The ESP32 `ecghelper` firmware logs estimated ECG amplitudes in mV with fixed conversion factors determined by measuring the calibration signal. Amplitudes in Linux `offlineecg` use arbitrary units.

Figure A.5: Calibration signals: Scope view of the built-in ± 0.5 mV pulse (blue raw, red after FIR filter, yellow QRS filter, green edges QRS events) and analysis of 60 ms pulses generated by the Fluke PS420 simulator

Figure A.5 shows the amplitude calibration signal from the built-in source, while figure 2.9 shows the step response to an external signal at different stages of processing: The raw signal is distorted by the analogue high-pass filter of the wing and the FIR filtering causes additional ringing, but also reduces higher frequency artifacts. A compensation filter applied to the averaged data significantly reduces the distortion caused by the analogue high-pass. There is no compensation step in the software for the FIR ringing, but in ECG signals, only the QRS complexes have sufficiently steep edges to be noticeably affected, increasing their peak amplitudes somewhat.

The Linux application does not use any type of amplitude calibration. It does use built-in automatic gain control heuristics instead: Weak signals are amplified by a suitable power of two factor to reach the dynamic range expected by the processing algorithm. Automatic smoothing steps with 1, 2, 1 kernel are inserted to avoid the introduction stair-step artefacts for large gain factors. In addition, the Linux version checks the dynamic range of data files in quintiles of 20 percent of the time axis and skips the first one or two quintiles if their dynamic ranges are too different from the rest of the recording. This avoids processing of set-up artefacts as part of the ECG and is done in a recursive fashion. Failure to find QRS complexes at a plausible range also is handled by similar skip-start-and-retry heuristics, also recursively. Should too little input data remain (compile-time configured threshold 8 seconds), further skipping is suppressed and even low-quality data will be used.

B Appendix: Source Code Details

B.1 Design Parameters and Constants

The system collects up to 30 seconds of ECG, or 25 heart beats, whichever happens first. The offline Linux application can be reconfigured to read up to 2 minutes of ECG: Most array indices are unsigned 16 bit to ease porting to small embedded systems. The ECG morphology analysis checks up to 1.5 seconds of data. Memory use is dominated by the recording buffer, which holds 16 bit per sample for, in the current configuration, up to 30 seconds (30000 bytes) of ECG recordings.

Another buffer of the same size exists for slope / derivative data, but that latter can be disabled at the cost of making periodogram analysis use far more CPU, repeatedly calculating the same derivatives. If the buffer is enabled and existence of AC hum could be detected beforehand, dedicated analysis time could be reduced by calculating slopes already in the recording phase. The Linux application defines MINDURATION as 8 (seconds) as the shortest recording worth analysing.

The Linux application has a 640 by 480 pixel, 1 byte per pixel drawing canvas buffer for graphical output, while the ESP32 embedded software has no local canvas, but sends drawing commands to an external colour OLED (organic light emitting diode) display with built-in controller and memory.

Most MAX30003 ECG analogue front-end configuration settings can only be modified by changing driver source code, but are not expected to change frequently. All code about timing expects 500 samples per second, or 2 ms per sample. Filters are short to keep real-time latency low: 18 ms of FIR latency for the optimised 50 Hz comb notch, 58 ms for the QRS feature (see figure 1.1) detection and 34 ms for smooth slope measurement. The latter is not yet computed in the real-time phase, as detection of unexpected 60 / 187 Hz AC hum is done only after recording. Slope filter length affects how close to segment edges slopes can be measured, so this filter, too, should be kept short.

A few important constants defined in headers (and code) include PQRWINDOW, the P-wave search window size before R (125 samples or 250 ms, dynamically limited at high pulse rates), RSEARCHWIDTH and OPTIMRANGE (75 samples, can be less) to pinpoint R peaks around QRS feature peaks. SMOOTHEXCLUDE (+/- 30 samples, 10 if AC hum present) controls the maximum QRS size protected from smoothing for morphology analysis. Matching the periodogram scoring, FLUTTERTHRESHOLD and FLUTTERRISKTHRESHOLD define when spectral scores are to be seen as a-fib or a-fib suspect, respectively. Other periodogram related constants are PERIOSMOOTH (number of smoothing passes) and HUMTHRESHOLD, which controls when 50, 60 and (empirically found while inspecting corpus data using FFT) 187.25 Hz AC hum filter stages activate.

PTHFACTOR sets the fraction which P-wave amplitude has to reach relative to R: While the factor of 1/43 may seem very low, it also has to account for averaging losses and has empirically been found to be appropriate. QRSMINTHRESHOLD and QRSMAXTHRESHOLD (16*16 and 80*80) limit the range in which QRS detection thresholds can dynamically adapt and have been selected to match the circa 4000 units dynamic range of the Einthoven lead I signal at 80 V/V gain in the embedded system. To match that, the Linux offline tool applies a power of two gain to reach 3500 to 8000 units dynamic range.

Other constants which appear directly in the source code without having names: Constants from the Sagie QTc correction formula, QTc and R/R limits for averaging segments, RMS (root mean square) value and RMS difference limits relative to mean or minimum for selecting a subset of heartbeats for averaging, zones around R which are reserved for QRS complexes and not searched for P- or T-waves, slope limits for average pulse shape regression analysis detrending and baseline amplitude measurements, minimum number of averaged heartbeats to be able to run a-fib classification (3 for recorded, 9 for real-time data), P-wave asymmetry limits (steepest ascent at least 4 times as far from peak as steepest descent is suspicious), PR starting at start of search zone or more than 240 ms before R peak are rejected (no proper P found, onset has no clear timing), PR below 120 ms (for

R/R below 320 ms: 100 ms) or above 205 ms is suspicious, averaged P-wave duration must be 28 to 130 ms and above 120 ms or below 45 ms (lower at high pulse rates) is suspicious.

The periodogram is computed up to $5/4$ of the R/R, at most 260 samples, but only periods up to 5 samples below $1/2$ R/R are considered for a-fib risk scoring. Periods 13 to 50 are not currently scored and seem to correspond to either a-fib or muscle artefacts, but periods 50 to 170 have most influence on the score, followed by 170 to 200 samples and finally 200 to 250 samples. In terms of frequencies, this corresponds to highest weights for 3 to 10 Hz components, followed by 2.5 to 3 Hz and 2 to 2.5 Hz components. The periodogram area also is scored here.

For smoothing the derivative to compute periodograms while AC hum is present, 5, 8 or 10 sample windows are used if 187.25, 60 or 50 Hz hum are the main source of artefacts. Note that most 50 Hz hum is already filtered out by the initial optimised 50 Hz comb notch filter, so the additional slope smoothing rarely activates. Data from online ECG corpora does tend to contain 60 Hz or sometimes 187.25 Hz hum, though. If smooth derivatives are not used, the periodogram is instead smoothed several times with a short kernel. Scoring only considers peaks of at least $5/255$ height, normalised to by definition $255/255$ height at period 0, and only periods below $1/2$ R/R.

More elaborate filter kernels, explained in sections 2.2.1, 2.2.2 and 2.3, are the 18 tap optimised 50 Hz comb notch, 63 tap QRS detection feature filter and 34 tap (prepared to switch to 18 tap) truncated binomial derivative filter for slope calculations. All filters use 32-bit fixed point arithmetic for low CPU load on embedded hardware, although the ESP32 does have some floating point support.

Most aspects of the graphical output geometry, layout and colour are fixed in the `offlineecg` or `ecghelper` code respectively, although some aspects are controlled by defines in headers.

R/R periods outside 250 to 1500 ms (or 1750 ms) range will be off-scale in some plots and R/R below 250 ms (or below 390 ms and less than $7/10$ of mean R/R) are subject to fusion in the analysis step.

The Pan/Tompkins inspired QRS feature threshold tracking updates as $5/6$ old value plus $1/6$ new value and the later R alignment optimiser stage switches to S alignment if S amplitude is at least 3 times the R amplitude.

B.2 Hardware Specific Headers

The `ecghelper` application for ESP32 contains system-specific code for energy saving, the MAX30003 analogue front-end, a small colour OLED display, NeoPixel colour LED and logging over an USB (Universal Serial Bus) debug port: The ESP32 board has an USB serial converter chip which is also used for in-circuit programming, output can be displayed using the Arduino IDE.

Logging could be redirected to a Bluetooth serial stream, as the default firmware for ESP32 on Arduino already includes all wireless drivers for Bluetooth and wireless network. However, wireless communication, in particular via WLAN (WiFi network) can cause significant energy consumption. One of the two ESP32 CPU cores is reserved for wireless controller tasks.

The application is compiled in Arduino IDE available from <https://arduino.cc/> which also provides comprehensive information about Arduino specific headers and functions. You will have to install support for Adafruit ESP32 Feather and the ESP32 Espressif toolchain: Add https://raw.githubusercontent.com/espressif/arduino-esp32/gh-pages/package_esp32_index.json to the Arduino IDE board manager URL (world wide web Uniform Resource Locator), list, in settings, then install `esp32` in the board manager menu, in tools / board, which will make a list of boards in the ESP32 Arduino category available. Select Adafruit ESP32 Feather for the HUZZAH32. Compiling and firmware upload (via USB serial) are menu items in the IDE. Note that projects (sketches) have to contain an empty file `component.mk` in the project directory for proper multi-file linking.

Upload speeds of up to 921600 baud should be no problem. The default clock speed of 80 MHz is recommended for the application: It has not been tested at (lower power) speeds of 40 MHz or below. The firmware option without OTA (over the air) is sufficient: OTA would support firmware updates over wireless LAN, as the ESP32 supports both wireless LAN and Bluetooth as part of the default firmware and has one CPU core dedicated to that by default. A verbose core debug level will send error messages through the USB serial line in case of a crash (division by zero, overflows, FreeRTOS real-time OS timing issues) while sending very few messages during normal operations.

The only library which is used which is not already part of the default set for Adafruit ESP32 Feather are the ESP32 Digital RGB LED Drivers which provide a fast communication channel for controlling the serial NeoPixel colour LED used in this project. The code written by Martin Falatic in 2017 can be used under the MIT License (Massachusetts Institute of Technology License), which requires the inclusion of the copyright notice and the license text when distributing the software, while granting comprehensive, free permissions for use and distribution:

<https://github.com/MartyMacGyver/ESP32-Digital-RGB-LED-Drivers>

A chain of NeoPixels can be driven by a single GPIO pin: They chain as large shift register (3 times 8 bit of R, G, B data for each LED) using a pulse width modulated serial code. To not overload the voltage regulator of the Feather, all 15 LED are limited to 1/8 of the maximum brightness in software, which already is very bright for signalling purposes, in particular when compared to the brightness of the small 96 by 64 pixel OLED colour display used in this project.

To avoid 50 Hz AC harmonics artefacts and for patient security, it is recommend to use the device only with non-mains power supplies such as USB power banks, or a laptop running on battery power, while there are electrodes connected to the patient. When using a laptop, the USB connection also transmits log data which can be viewed using the built-in serial monitor of the Arduino IDE.

As a compile-time option, it also is possible to create a plotter version of the software: This sends four integer values of data for each sample (2 ms per sample, 500 samples per second), as space separated text, both during recording and for the analysis results. The data can be visualised using the built-in serial plotter of the Arduino IDE, which implements automatic range selection (a sometimes annoying feature) and a scrolling scope view of the most recent 500 lines of data received at any time. As all other text messages are disabled while plotting, the non-plot version is recommended for everyday use: It writes ECG metrics for the recorded data to the serial monitor.

Since the ESP32 comes with built-in Bluetooth, it would be interesting to redirect the log data stream from USB to Bluetooth: That way, logs can be viewed on devices powered by 230 V mains power supplies without the risk of introducing measurement artefacts. The risks for the patient are low even in the USB connected case, as the hardware has 50 k Ω series resistors for the (ESD protected) main ECG leads, a 500 k Ω leg drive series resistor and much higher internal impedances. Also, computer ports and cases are generally safe to touch even without series resistors.

The only powersave function used yet disables wireless communications.

```

1 #ifndef _POWERSAVE_H
2 #define _POWERSAVE_H
3
4 #include <Arduino.h>           // includes many common other *.h
5 #include <WiFi.h>             // just to save power
6 #include <driver/adc.h>       // just to save power
7 #include <esp_bt.h>           // just to save power
8 #include <esp_wifi.h>        // just to save power
9
10 /* Disable power-hungry wireless interfaces: WiFi, Bluetooth etc. */
11 void disableWireless(void);
12
13 #endif

```

Listing 1: Powersave functions: Disable wireless communications to save energy

The driver for the MAX30003 is an essential part of the embedded software.

```

1 #ifndef _MAX30003_H
2 #define _MAX30003_H
3
4 #include <Arduino.h> // esp32-hal.h etc.
5
6 #include <SPI.h>
7 // Default: FSPI flash, HSPI pins 12 to 15, VSPI 5/18/19/23, clock 1 MHz
8 // setFrequency: 125000 Hz * 2 ^ n, max 8 MHz?
9
10 // 1 for hardware SPI, 0 for software implementation
11 #define ECGHWSPI 1
12
13 // #define DEBUGECGSPI
14
15 // MAX30003 specifies 0 to 12000000 Hz as valid SPI clocks
16 #define ECGSPEED 8000000
17 // chip select
18 #define ECGCS 15
19 // SPI clock
20 #define ECGCLK 5
21 // SPI data to MAX30003
22 #define ECGMOSI 18
23 // SPI data from MAX30003
24 #define ECGMISO 19
25 // interrupt pin for events, if MAX30003 programmed to send interrupts
26 #define ECGINT 33
27
28 /* Read MAX30003 ECG AFE register, full transaction */
29 uint32_t ecgReadFull(uint8_t reg);
30
31 /* Write MAX30003 ECG AFE register, full transaction */
32 uint32_t ecgWriteFull(uint8_t reg, uint32_t value);
33
34 // reset the FIFO and flush buffers
35 #define ecgResetFIFO() ecgWriteFull(10, 0x000000)
36
37 // read the 24 bit status flag register
38 #define ecgReadStatus() ecgReadFull(1)
39
40 // read a tagged data word as 24 bit value from the FIFO
41 #define ecgReadFIFO() ecgReadFull(33)
42
43 /* Read MAX30003 R/R period register and return value converted to ms */
44 uint32_t ecgReadRR();
45
46 /* Ensure GPIO pins are set to the proper directions */
47 void ecgInitEarly();
48
49 /* Configure MAX30003 ECG Analog Front End and start recording */
50 void ecgInit();
51
52 #endif

```

Listing 2: MAX30003 functions: Communication with integrated SPI ECG analogue front-end

The user interface peripherals also require drivers: OLED display and NeoPixel LED.

```

1 #ifndef _OLED_H
2 #define _OLED_H
3
4 #include <Arduino.h> // esp32-hal.h etc.
5
6 #include <SPI.h>
7 // Default: FSPI flash, HSPI pins 12 to 15, VSPI 5/18/19/23, clock 1 MHz

```

```

8 // setFrequency: 125000 Hz * 2 ^ n, max 8 MHz?
9
10 #include "ecgmath.h" // saturate() etc.
11
12 // command 0xa0: 0x60 interlaced RGB565, 0x70 same Y-flipped (or 2: X-flipped)
13 // Bit 0: 0 increase column after each pixel, wrap to next line in bitmap mode
14 // (1 increase rows first, wrap to next column, "vertical address inc mode")
15 // Bit 1: Flip columns in display rendering (X-flipping)
16 // Bit 2: Use BGR instead of RGB subpixel order
17 // Bit 3: Flip ROWS electrically (interlaced: adjacent, non-i: 0..31 / 32..63)
18 // Bit 4: Flip ROW scan direction (Y-flipping)
19 // Bit 5: Enable ROW interlacing (0, 2, 4... or flipped 1, 3, 5...)
20 // Bits 7 and 6: Bitmap data mode (00 byte 332, 01 packed 565, 10 three bytes)
21 // (3 byte format uses the 6 low bits of each byte and ignores R / B LSB)
22 // 0x60: 01 100 000, 0x70: 01 110 000
23 #define OLEDCONFIG 0x70
24
25 // in theory, SSD1331 can handle up to 13.3 MHz SPI clock
26 #define OLEDSPEED 8000000
27 // GPIO26 OLED data, GPIO25 OLED clock, GPIO17 OLED nCS, GPIO4 OLED D/nC
28 // PROBLEM: GPIO34, GPIO39, GPIO36 can NOT be used as output...
29 #define OLEDDATA 26
30 #define OLEDCLK 25
31 #define OLEDCS 17
32 #define OLEDDC 4
33
34 // SSD1331 has max 13 1/3 MHz SPI clock: Min 18 ESP32 cycles/bit at 240 MHz
35 // To find out how software SPI is: ~/.arduino15/packages/esp32/tools/
36 // xtensa-esp32-elf-gcc/*/bin/xtensa-esp32-elf-objdump
37 // -d /run/user/*/arduino/arduino_build_*/sketch/ecg_test.ino.cpp.o but ...
38 // ... it turns out digitalWrite esp32-hal-gpio.c.o takes 13+4 instructions:
39 // true/false? block 1/2? write 1<<n to either out or out1, wlts or wlts!
40 // and digitalWrite is not inlined, but called: 4 instructions per call.
41
42 // to set 1 pixel, set X and Y ranges and send first bitmap pixel of range!
43 // controller also has various palette tricks, rectangular blitting etc.
44
45 /* Make sure GPIO for OLED are configured to the right directions */
46 void oledInitEarly();
47
48 /* Setup interface to OLED display and initialize OLED controller */
49 void oledInit();
50
51 /* draw a line, color values can be 0 to 255 but actual color depth is lower */
52 void oledLine(uint8_t x1, uint8_t y1, uint8_t x2, uint8_t y2,
53             uint8_t r, uint8_t g, uint8_t b);
54
55 /* draw a rectangle, color values can be 0 to 255, actual color depth lower
56 * if filled == true, fill in the same color, else draw only border
57 */
58 void oledRect(uint8_t x1, uint8_t y1, uint8_t x2, uint8_t y2, uint8_t r,
59             uint8_t g, uint8_t b, uint8_t filled);
60
61 #define BITMAPX 0
62 #define BITMAPY 1
63 #define BITMAP0 2
64
65 /* transmit a complete bitmap image, type 0 next pixel is next column,
66 * type 1 next pixel is next row, type 2 image is blank, others reserved
67 */
68 void oledBitmap(uint8_t x1, uint8_t y1, uint8_t x2, uint8_t y2,
69             uint8_t type, const uint16_t *pixels);
70
71 /* Draw a vertical line using a static gradient sprite: Pixels with the same
72 * Y coordinate always get the same RGB value. Looks nicer than plain lines.

```

```

73  */
74  void oledGradientLineY(uint8_t x, uint8_t y1, uint8_t y2);
75  #endif

```

Listing 3: OLED functions: Graphics primitives for SPI colour OLED display

The NeoPixel driver is a small wrapper around a third-party library.

```

1  #ifndef _NEOPIXEL_H
2  #define _NEOPIXEL_H
3
4  #include <Arduino.h>           // includes many common other *.h
5
6  #include <esp32_digital_led_lib.h>
7
8  // for additional neopixel functionality see esp32_digital_led_lib.h
9
10 #define LEDCOUNT 15
11
12 // #pragma GCC diagnostic push
13 // #pragma GCC diagnostic ignored "-Wmissing-field-initializers" // avoid -Wall
14 // noise
15
16 // RX/16 is data pin (brightLimit only for rainbows) NOTE: WS2812B, not WS2813B!
17 // WARNING: Each LED 3x20 mA, too bright, too much power! 1/8 is bright enough!
18 // BUG: Adjacent LED pixel pairs can sometimes get stuck to share colors!
19 // (when that happens, sending color A B C D etc. shows as A B B C D etc.)
20
21 /* Setup the NeoPixel array driver */
22 void initNeoPixels(void);
23
24 /* Update the NeoPixel RGB LED: Send strand data via serial line */
25 void updateNeoPixels(void);
26
27 /* Set the RGB data of the selected pixel (no automatic sending to LED!) */
28 void setNeoPixel(uint8_t n, uint8_t r, uint8_t g, uint8_t b);
29
30 /* Reset the RGB data of the selected pixel (not automatic sending to LED!) */
31 #define backgroundPixel(x) setNeoPixel((x), (x) >> 1, ((LEDCOUNT - (x)) >> 1), 0);
32
33 /* Set the selected pixel to a heatmap-based color: 0..255 = K..R..Y..W..B
34  * (no automatic refresh of the NeoPixel LEDs, have to send manually!)
35  */
36 void heatPixel(uint8_t col, uint8_t heat);
37
38 #endif

```

Listing 4: NeoPixel functions: Controls a chain of serial colour LED

Logging and global settings depend on whether embedded system or Linux application are used.

```

1  #ifndef _LOGTOOLS_H
2  #define _LOGTOOLS_H
3
4  // NOTE: HardwareSerial implements Stream, as does BluetoothSerial :- )
5  #include <HardwareSerial.h>    // log and plot output via Serial.print...
6
7  // Set to 0 or 1 for low or high verbosity levels
8  #define VERBOSE 1
9  // NOTE: PLOTTER disables almost all output apart from 3 columns of plot data
10
11 #define logInt(a) Serial.print(a)
12 #define logIntLN(a) Serial.println(a)
13 #define logIntNewline(a) Serial.println(a)
14
15 #define logHex(a) Serial.print(a, HEX)

```

```

16 #define logHexLN(a) Serial.println(a, HEX)
17 #define logHexNewline(a) Serial.println(a, HEX)
18
19 #define logString(a) Serial.print(a)
20 #define logStringLN(a) Serial.println(a)
21 #define logStringNewline(a) Serial.println(a)
22
23 #define logLN() Serial.println()
24 #define logNewline() Serial.println()
25
26 #endif

```

Listing 5: ecghelper logtools configuration: Log via USB serial port

The global configuration is shared with the Linux application, using conditional defines.

```

1 #ifndef _ECGHELPER_H
2 #define _ECGHELPER_H
3
4 #include "logtools.h" // the global place to modify logging for this app
5
6 /* CONFIGURATION SETTINGS */
7
8 #ifndef __linux__
9 // define to output data for Arduino IDE serial plotter instead of other messages
10 // #define PLOTTER 1
11 #endif
12
13 // define to apply software baseline tracking: Not necessary on ESP32, the
14 // MAX30003 has a built-in analog HPF (0.44 or 0.5 Hz for MAX30003WING board)
15 // and an optional 1st order 0.5 Hz IIR HPF, which is disabled in max30003.cpp
16 #ifdef __linux__
17 // NOTE: Should only be necessary for VERY baseline wander distorted data files
18 // #define SOFTBASELINE 1
19 #else
20 // NOTE: Software baseline tracking theoretically allows inverse filter for shape
21 // #define SOFTBASELINE 1
22 #endif
23
24 #ifndef __linux__
25 // define to use built-in calibration voltage test "QRS" with 512 sample R/R
26 // NOTE: after 50 Hz comb FIR, baseline ca. Q -270 R 3110 S -610, 3720 LSB/mV
27 // #define CALIBRATION 1
28 #endif
29
30 // define to disable wireless (wifi, bluetooth etc.) from 80-260 to < 35 mA
31 #define POWERSAVE 1
32 // NOTE: sleep modes 3 to 800 uA, but wake is reboot, only RTC data preserved
33
34 // height of scope window
35 #define SCOPEY 64
36
37 // width of scope window
38 #define SCOPEX 95
39
40 // GPIO13 is connected to a red LED on the ESP32 HUZZAH32 feather board:
41 #define REDLED LED_BUILTIN /* 13 */
42
43 #endif

```

Listing 6: ecghelper general configuration header

B.3 Linux Application

The Linux `offlineecg` application logs to the standard output stream, using simple `stdio` functions. To compile the Linux version, simply use:

```
gcc -Warray-bounds=2 -Wpedantic -Wextra -O2 -o offlineecg -Wall *.cpp
```

It is possible to compile with the `-pg` option, then run the application once on a large number of files then use the profiling tool `gprof -b offlineecg gmon.out > gprof.txt` to create a text file which gives an overview how much time has been spent in which functions during that run.

To run the application on any batch size of files, invoke:

```
./offlineecg filename1.eric otherfilename.eric etc.
```

Output files will be created as `/tmp/pcx/filename1.pcx`, `/tmp/pcx/otherfilename.pcx` and so on. If the directory does not exist or is not writable, no files will be created! If only one input file is given, the application will instead create a file `ecgplot.pcx` in the current working directory, independent of the name and location of the input data file.

The data files are expected to be raw, headerless signed 16-bit binary data files in the byte order (endianness) of the used CPU, one channel, recorded at a rate of 500 samples per second.

If the file name ends with `_INV.eric`, the sample data values will be sign-flipped before use. This is to allow quick manual corrections of swapped lead recordings, without having to change file contents and without having to rely on data analysis to automatically spot lead swap errors in ECG recordings.

Analysis results will be printed to standard output, so it is a good idea to redirect that to a logfile for later review, in particular if a large number of files will be processed. As a compile time option, either verbose output or less verbose output can be selected.

```

1 #ifndef _LOGTOOLS_H
2 #define _LOGTOOLS_H
3
4 #include <stdio.h>
5
6 // set to either 0 or 1, for less or more verbose output
7 #define VERBOSE 1
8
9 #define logInt(a) printf("%d", a)
10 #define logIntLN(a) printf("%d\n", a)
11 #define logIntNewline(a) printf("%d\n", a)
12
13 #define logHex(a) printf("%x", a)
14 #define logHexLN(a) printf("%x\n", a)
15 #define logHexNewline(a) printf("%x\n", a)
16
17 #define logString(a) printf("%s", a)
18 #define logStringLN(a) puts(a) /* printf("%s\n", a) */
19 #define logStringNewline(a) puts(a) /* printf("%s\n", a) */
20
21 #define logLN() puts("") /* printf("\n") */
22 #define logNewline() puts("") /* printf("\n") */
23
24 #endif

```

Listing 7: `offlineecg` logtools configuration: Log via standard output

B.4 Hardware Independent Headers

The most generic file here is `ecgmath`, with mathematical basics such as square root or array mean.

```

1  #ifndef _ECGMATH_H
2  #define _ECGMATH_H
3
4  #include <stdint.h> // uintXX_t, intXX_t etc.
5
6  #define saturate(a, lo, hi) (((a) < (lo)) ? (lo) : (((a) > (hi)) ? (hi) : (a)))
7
8  #define limitto(a, hi) (((a) > hi) ? (hi) : (a))
9
10 #define setarray(data, len, val) for (uint16_t i=0; i<(len); i++) { data[i] = (val)→
    →; }
11
12 /* integer square root approximation */
13 uint16_t intsqr(uint32_t n);
14
15 /* Estimate RMS amplitude of some data, overflow-proof */
16 uint16_t dataRMS(const int16_t *data, uint16_t len);
17
18 /* Estimate RMS deviation between two recordings, NOT overflow-proof:
19  * WARNING: Overflow is likely to occur if RMSD > sqrt(maxint / len)
20  */
21 uint16_t dataRMSD(const int16_t *data1, const int16_t *data2, uint16_t len);
22
23 /* Compute mean value of an int16_t data vector */
24 int16_t dataMean(const int16_t *data, uint16_t len);
25
26 /* Find index of largest value in int16_t data vector,
27  * optionally update the specified value variable if not NULL
28  */
29 uint16_t findMaxIndex(const int16_t *data, uint16_t len, int16_t *maxval);
30
31 /* Find index of smallest or most negative value in int16_t data vector
32  * optionally update the specified value variable if not NULL
33  */
34 uint16_t findMinIndex(const int16_t *data, uint16_t len, int16_t *minval);
35
36 /* Output some data array over Serial, with line breaks every 8 values
37  * Items which are outside the specified range are skipped
38  */
39 void logUnsignedArray(const uint16_t *data, uint16_t len, uint16_t min, uint16_t →
    →max);
40
41 #endif

```

Listing 8: `ecgmath` functions: Basic mathematical building blocks

The real-time (or initial file processing) phase relies on filters and baseline.

```

1  #ifndef _FILTERS_H
2  #define _FILTERS_H
3
4  #include <stdint.h> // uintXX_t, intXX_t etc.
5
6  // Hardware QRS latency: 125 sps processing (8 ms granularity)
7  // 105 ms QRS detector delay and 32 ms LPF delay (20 ms decimator-only)
8  // subtract (!) 36 ms latency of software FIR N * 50 Hz notch and, if used,
9  // 1024 ms baseline moving average latency, (AVGBUFSIZE/2)*2ms, = -923 ms?
10 // to align to ecgdata[now + software latency - chip latency]
11 #ifdef SOFTBASELINE
12 // NOTE: RRLATENCY is negative with SOFTBASELINE, MAX30003 notices QRS first
13 // #define RRLATENCY ((105+32) - (AVGBUFSIZE+36))

```

```

14 // empirically, latency seems to be 230 ms more, -693 ms?
15 // NOTE: BASELINEDELAYSAMPLES is defined in baseline.h
16 #define RRLATENCY (230 + (105 + 32) - ((BASELINEDELAYSAMPLES*2) + 36))
17 #else // no ESP32 baseline tracking, just MAX30003WING analog high-pass filter
18 // NOTE: RRLATENCY is positive without SOFTBASELINE, ESP32 notices QRS first
19 // empirically corrected latency of +344 ms, std circa 17 ms
20 #define RRLATENCY (243 + (105 + 32) - 36)
21 #endif
22
23 // delay of FIR comb filter to block AC harmonics
24 #define FIRLATENCY 9
25
26 // delay of QRS detector in SAMPLES, to align to the ECG peak, for
27 // display and for averaging. 31.5 in theory, but 29 fits reality
28 #define QRSLATENCY 29
29
30 /* Initialize or reset all filter related variables and buffers */
31 void initFilters(void);
32
33 /* Use 1 sample and 17 previous samples to compute 1 FIR filtered sample
34 * (which will be based on a filter centered around a delay of 9 samples)
35 */
36 int16_t firFilter(int16_t sample);
37
38 /* Use 1 sample and 62 previous samples to compute 1 QRS peak evidence
39 * sample, based on a smoothed second derivative, center of delay being
40 * 31.5 samples here
41 */
42 uint16_t qrsFilter(int16_t sample);
43
44 /* Smooth an averaged pulse shape in a QRS preserving way given the
45 * assumption that the R peak is located at the given sample index,
46 * for 500 sps data. Optionally apply 8 sample moving average if
47 * has60hz is set, to suppress 60 Hz AC hum and harmonics of it
48 */
49 void ecgSmoothing(int16_t *data, uint16_t rindex, uint16_t len, bool has60hz);
50
51 /* Calculate smoothed derivative (slope) vector for data vector */
52 void slopeFilter(const int16_t *data, int16_t *slope, uint16_t len);
53
54 #endif

```

Listing 9: filters functions: Several optimised custom FIR filters

```

1 #ifndef _BASELINE_H
2 #define _BASELINE_H
3
4 #include <stdint.h> // uint16_t etc.
5
6 // latency of baseline filter in samples
7 #define BASELINEDELAYSAMPLES 512
8
9 // length of long-term moving average for baseline drift tracking, 2^N
10 #define AVGBUFSIZE (2 * BASELINEDELAYSAMPLES)
11
12 /* Init and reset baseline and range tracking */
13 void initBaseline(void);
14
15 /* Return zero if averager in normal operation, otherwise
16 * return number of samples until averager init has will complete
17 */
18 uint16_t getBaselineLockout(void);
19
20 /* Apply moving average baseline correction to sample */
21 int16_t baselineCorrect(int16_t sample);

```

```

22
23 /* Request switch to a new value range epoch: Will happen at a suitable
24 * upcoming updateRange() call, considering which values are seen. Call
25 * this for example after each QRS complex / R peak detection moment.
26 * Timeout is how many updateRange() calls the switch can wait at most.
27 */
28 void recycleRange(uint16_t timeout);
29
30 /* Return current minimum of value range */
31 int16_t getRangeMin(void);
32
33 /* Return current maximum of value range */
34 int16_t getRangeMax(void);
35
36 /* Enforce new minimum of value range */
37 void setRangeMin(int16_t newmin);
38
39 /* Enforce new maximum of value range */
40 void setRangeMax(int16_t newmax);
41
42 /* Review sample to update knowledge of min / max value range of samples:
43 * Samples outside any range immediately grow the ranges. One range tracks
44 * the used value range since last recycling ranges, switching for that at
45 * a suitable moment allows zooming into signals again after artifacts etc.
46 */
47 void updateRange(int16_t sample);
48
49 #endif

```

Listing 10: baseline functions: Baseline tracking by 2 second moving average

While qrsfind works in the early or real-time phase, rrttools optimizes ECG segmentation offline.

```

1 #ifndef _QRSFIND_H
2 #define _QRSFIND_H
3
4 #include <stdint.h> // uint16_t etc.
5
6 // Pan Tompkins style tracking of R peaks and their detection thresholds etc.
7
8 // time in samples for learning how strong peaks can get (e.g. 1.5s, 750 samples)
9 #define QRSLEARN 750
10 // time in samples to skip after each QRS complex (e.g. 200 ms, 100 samples)
11 #define QRSLOCKOUT 110
12
13 // minimal expected peak metric for threshold tracking (e.g. square of 16)
14 #define QRSMINTHRESHOLD 256
15
16 // maximal tracked peak metric for threshold tracking (e.g. square of 64, 80, 96)
17 #define QRSMAXTHRESHOLD 6400
18
19 /* Init and reset QRS search state */
20 void initQRSDetector(void);
21
22 /* Return the QRS lockout state: usually 0, but right after the
23 * detection of a QRS complex, the value is the number of upcoming
24 * samples during which no QRS complexes will be considered. In
25 * other words: Non-zero if the detector recently saw some R peak
26 */
27 uint16_t getQRSLockout(void);
28
29 /* Send next sample into a signal processing queue for qRs complex detection,
30 * using a FIR filter based frequency specific peak detector and Pan Tompkins
31 * style tracking of detection thresholds. Either log detected R/R specs or
32 * log plot-friendly data including (delayed) samples and R/R metrics. Record

```

```

33  * the detected R/R timestamps and periods for later use. NOTE: timestamp will
34  * be adjusted by QRSLATENCY * sampling period (2 ms / sample at 500 sps). The
35  * alignedsample value is only used to plot QRS metrics and sample in parallel.
36  * Return true at the moment of a detected R peak / QRS complex
37  */
38  bool rrDetector(int16_t sample, uint16_t timestamp, int16_t alignedsample);
39
40 #endif

```

Listing 11: qrsfind functions: Pan Tompkins inspired R/R detection

```

1  #ifndef _RRTOOLS_H
2  #define _RRTOOLS_H
3
4  #include <stdint.h> // uint16_t etc.
5
6  // how many samples in either direction to search for higher peaks
7  // NOTE: 30 is plenty for normal pinpointing, 75 to fix "P-as-R" mistakes
8  #define RSEARCHWIDTH 75
9
10 // how many samples (2 ms each) to search around R for other polarity peaks
11 // NOTE: must be at least RSEARCHWIDTH to preserve inverted R as such
12 #define OPTIMRANGE RSEARCHWIDTH
13
14 // how many samples on either side to use to get an idea of the baseline
15 #define RBASEWIDTH (RSEARCHWIDTH * 2)
16
17 // capacity of temp buffers for R/R processing, as number of R/R events
18 #define RRTEMPBUFSIZE 100
19
20 /* Log R/R timestamps and periods, with label ("MAX30003" or "software")
21  * and suppressing values which are 0 or more than tmax
22  */
23 void rrLogData(const uint16_t *times, const uint16_t *periods, uint16_t len, const →
    →char *label, uint16_t tmax);
24
25 /* pinpoint exact R peak moments and update R/R data
26  * Input: approximate R times (in samples!), ECG data
27  * Output: R times get updated
28  */
29 void rrOptimizer(uint16_t *rtimes, uint16_t len, const int16_t *ecg, uint16_t →
    →ecglen);
30
31 /* Create RR period list from R time list (both use the same time units)
32  * The first RR item is rtimes[1] - rtimes[0] and so on. Items which would
33  * be more than tmax are set to 0 (invalid) instead.
34  */
35 void rTimesToRR(const uint16_t *rtimes, uint16_t *rrperiods, uint16_t len, uint16_t →
    →tmax);
36
37 /* Compute and log mean of all valid R/R periods, as well as beats per minute,
38  * based on the given list of R times (in milliseconds) and skipping all cases
39  * where the period is either 0 or more than ecglen.
40  */
41 int16_t rrMeanLog(const uint16_t *rtimes, uint16_t rlen, uint16_t ecglen, bool log) →
    →;
42
43 #endif

```

Listing 12: rrttools functions: Postprocessing of collected R/R data

The ecganalysis functions coordinate the non real-time stage: Per-beat segments are evaluated and selected segments are pooled by averaging.

```

1 #ifndef _ECGANALYSIS_H
2 #define _ECGANALYSIS_H
3
4 #include <stdint.h> // uint16_t etc.
5
6 #define ECGGOOD 1
7 #define ECGOKAY 2
8 #define ECGBAD 3
9 #define ECGNOISY 4
10
11 // various temp buffer sizes in samples: Averaged ECG pulse must be shorter
12 #define EATEMPBUFSIZE 750
13
14 /* Analyze and display R/R and pulse data, log metrics: Use R times and ECG
15 * data, output judgement ECGGOOD, ECGOKAY, ECGBAD, ECGNOISY: Noisy means
16 * data has too strong artifacts to classify, good is better than okay, bad
17 * means ECG shows signs of atrial fibrillation (no good P wave detectable).
18 * The rrmean value is used to log QTc after QT period correction and to
19 * exclude (will update rtimes!) short beats, possible T QRS misdetections.
20 * Optionally write periodogram data for the first periolen shifts in the
21 * periodata array, unless that is NULL (max: periodata[0], magic value
22 * periodata[periolen - 1] == periodata[0] indicates AC filter active).
23 * Score contains up to 4 byte values: 128 unused, 1..127 bad, 128..255 good.
24 */
25 uint16_t ecgAnalysis(uint16_t *rtimes, uint16_t rlen, const int16_t *ecgdata, →
    →uint16_t ecglen, uint8_t *periodata, uint16_t periolen, int16_t rrmean, →
    →uint32_t *score);
26
27 // Prototypes which are not normally exported for outside use
28 #ifndef ECGANALYSIS_INTERNAL
29
30 // NOTE: If there is an RC HPF at the input, steps decay with  $w=1/RC$ ,
31 // so the proper compensation is to add the weighted integral again:
32 // for 0.5 Hz corner,  $w=2*\pi*fc=\pi$ , use 1/159 per sample at 500 sps
33 //
34 // The MAX30003 uses 450k (320k to 600k) as R and the MAX30003 wing uses
35 // 1 uF as HPF cap, so  $fc = 1/(2*\pi*R*C)$  is 0,354 Hz (0,265 to 0,497 Hz)
36 // so UNFILTERHPF would typically be 225, or between 160 and 311, with
37 // correction  $sample(i) += sum(sample 0..i) / UNFILTERHPF$  after DC removal
38 #ifndef __linux__
39 // NOTE: Use "too high" values to keep a bit of the decay active
40 #define UNFILTERHPF 192
41 #else // deactivate filter
42 #define UNFILTERHPF 0
43 #endif
44
45 // NOTE: showPulseShape is in either ecghelper.ino or offlineecg.cpp,
46 // depending on which gets compiled. Not very elegant?
47
48 /* extended average pulse shape display, with slope, markers and beat
49 * classification bitmap. Return the count of 1 bits in bitmap.
50 */
51 uint16_t showPulseShape(const int16_t *shape, const int16_t *slope, const uint8_t *→
    →markers, uint16_t len, uint32_t bitmap);
52
53 /* Compute average pulse shape by gathering excerpts around listed R times,
54 * output bitmap which of the first 32 beats got used. The averaged shape is
55 * stored in shape, updating (lowering) avglen to reflect the used duration.
56 * Beats shorter than a specific fraction of rrmean are not used for averaging
57 * and will be removed from rtimes (!). This may change the effective rrmean.
58 */
59 uint32_t ecgAveraging(uint16_t *rtimes, uint16_t rlen, const int16_t *ecgdata, →
    →uint16_t ecglen, int16_t *shape, uint16_t *avglen, uint16_t rrmean);
60
61 /* Use regression analysis of the first PQRWINDOW samples to (log and)

```

```

62  * remove a linear trend from those: Useful at high pulse rates when the
63  * T waves get close to the P waves. Updates shape (len: length of shape)
64  * Also shifts all samples to make the mean first PQRWINDOW samples 0.
65  */
66  void preQRSRegression(int16_t *shape, const uint16_t len);
67
68  /* center Y axis more around DC parts, rather than around the global mean */
69  void baselineCentering(int16_t *shape, int16_t *slope, uint16_t len);
70
71 #endif
72
73 #endif

```

Listing 13: ecganalysis functions: Central hub for final ECG analysis

After further normalisation, including pre-R regression and baseline adjustments, ecgshape functions process the averaged ECG pulse shape for one heartbeat to evaluate and log P-, QRS and T-waves. A P-wave score (in context of QRS) is generated for the atrial fibrillation or flutter classification.

```

1  #ifndef _ECGSHAPE_H
2  #define _ECGSHAPE_H
3
4  #include <stdint.h>          // uint16_t etc.
5  #include "ecganalysis.h"    // for return value constants
6
7  // NOTE: Use CALIBRATION compile time option to estimate LSB/mV after filters,
8  // activate in ecghelper.h – See max30003.cpp and ecgshape.cpp for details.
9  #define LSBPERMILLIVOLT 2500
10
11 // define to analyze other ECG metrics beyond P wave and R/R / QRS related
12 // ones: in particular, this enables T wave and QTc analysis
13 #define FULLECG 1
14
15 // samples before the R peak which are checked for a P wave (with filtering!)
16 // expected PQ 120–200 ms, 60–100 samples, same for PR. QRS is 80–120 ms wide
17 // NOTE: ecghelper.ino uses separate PQRWINDOW, may be max 150–(25+17+17)
18 // NOTE: values above 125 may show the peak of the previous T from 120 bpm!
19 #define PQRWINDOW 125
20
21 // minimal relative P height compared to either R-to-base or R-to-mean(Q,S)
22 // for example 35 for at least 1/35, or 40 for 1/40
23 #define PTHFACTOR 43
24
25 // minimal relative P height fraction for additional P waves, use 3 or 4 here
26 #define DOUBLEPFACTOR 3
27
28 /* Find a suitable base point to the right or left of a given start
29  * index, within given limits, and report the height of the resulting
30  * peak relative to the base. If stopindex < startindex, search back.
31  * Base expected to be lower than start, unless ushape set to invert.
32  * Also returns the found index of the base point.
33  * PLANNED to be able to skip over small wavy humps, max 10 samples.
34  */
35 int16_t findHalfPeak(const int16_t *shape, const int16_t *slope, uint16_t →
    →startindex, uint16_t stopindex, bool ushape, uint16_t *baseindex);
36
37 /* Analyze the provided single beat ECG pulse shape, using the provided smooth
38  * derivative slope data. Return judgement ECGGOOD, ECGOKAY, ECGBAD for good P
39  * wave and timings, good P wave with off timings or no detection of a P wave.
40  * The markers array will contain updated values corresponding to interesting
41  * samples or sample ranges, suitable for highlighting a pulse shape display.
42  * The rrmean value is used to log QTc with QT period correction and to avoid
43  * false P detections of the previous T wave. Score will be between 0 and 127
44  * for too shallow P waves and 128 to 255 for good P: Other factors can also
45  * cause lower scores in spite of existing P waves.

```

```

46  */
47  uint16_t analyzePulseShape(const int16_t *shape, const int16_t *slope, uint8_t *→
      →markers, uint16_t len, int16_t rrmean, uint8_t *score);
48
49  #endif

```

Listing 14: egshape functions: Morphological analysis of ECG data

The egsspectrum functions are invoked to generate a score from overall spectral properties using a periodogram of the derivative of the full ECG, used for the atrial fibrillation or flutter classification.

```

1  #ifndef _ECGSPECTRUM_H
2  #define _ECGSPECTRUM_H
3
4  #include <stdint.h> // uintXX_t, intXX_t etc.
5
6  // trigger level (-256 to 256) for 60 Hz or 50 Hz AC hum filter activation
7  // threshold -256 means always activate filter, 256 means never activate it:
8  // good values are significantly positive to avoid unnecessary filtering
9  #define HUMTHRESHOLD 9
10
11 // maximum used value for slopes, below 180 (sqrt(32k)) for worst case len 64k
12 // use even lower maximum to put less weight in periodicity of QRS complexes?
13 #define SLOPEMAX 128
14
15 // analyzePeriodogram() threshold above which ECG are rejected even with P-wave
16 // PS420 simulated a-fib have lower score, but have "double P" and "too early P"
17 // FLUTTERTHRESHOLD 650 is sufficient to catch most of the few P-unclear cases
18 #define FLUTTERTHRESHOLD 450
19
20 // analyzePeriodogram() threshold above which ECG with suspect P-wave are rejected
21 // values could be around 1/2 to 4/5 of FLUTTERTHRESHOLD, or 1/1 to disable this
22 #define FLUTTERISKTHRESHOLD 350
23
24 // maximum static buffer size for derivative: ECG longer than this need
25 // many slow repeated derivative computations in scaledAutocorrelation()
26 // could use #ifdef __linux__ here
27 #define SLOPEBUFSIZE 15000
28
29 /* Modified from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/PJW_hash_function
30 * Useful for keeping track of when data buffer contents change
31 */
32 uint32_t pjwHash(const int16_t *data, uint16_t len);
33
34 /* Return 255 times the autocorrelation of the data at the given shift
35 * period, optionally using a size N average (use 1 for normal operation,
36 * 8 smoothing filter to ignore 60 Hz AC harmonics, 10 for 50 Hz AC);
37 */
38 int32_t scaledAutocorrelation(const int16_t *data, const uint16_t len, const →
      →uint16_t period, const uint16_t smooth);
39
40 /* Periodogram analysis: Process ecgdata into periodogram (optionally,
41 * if not NULL, returns the first periolen items in periodata, fewer
42 * if less than periolen were relevant to the analysis) and return a
43 * a-fib / a-flutter score which can be used for classification etc.
44 * Also, periodata[periolen - 1] is set to periodata[0] if 50 Hz or
45 * 60 Hz AC hum has been found, to indicate that analysis has used
46 * moving average smoothed ECG derivatives.
47 */
48 uint16_t analyzePeriodogram(const int16_t *ecgdata, uint16_t ecglen, uint8_t *→
      →periodata, uint16_t periolen, int16_t rrmean);
49
50 #endif

```

Listing 15: egsspectrum functions: Spectral periodogram analysis of ECG data

